

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D6.6 – Neutrality Story Maps for Pilot Cities 1

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

Contact Email: contact@up2030-he.eu

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Reviewer(s)	Catalina Diaz (Fraunhofer), Constanza Vera (USTUTT)			
Abstract	<p>Deliverable 6.6 outlines the first version of the Neutrality Story Maps (NSM), a digital tool created as part of the UP2030 project to enhance citizen engagement in urban climate action. NSM integrates digital storytelling with geospatial mapping, allowing cities to communicate climate-related challenges and citizens to share their experiences and aspirations for climate neutrality. The tool's development is guided by a co-creative process involving pilot cities, ensuring it meets their specific needs and supports the project's goal of supporting the EU's climate neutrality 2030 goals.</p> <p>The document details the methodology used to gather user requirements through workshops, interviews, and surveys with city representatives and citizens. The initial feedback informed the design of the first version of the NSM platform, which features interactive stories geotagged on a map, promoting a participatory approach to urban planning. During the first iteration of co-design (M14-M18), aspects such as how to align the tool with pilot-specific goals, barriers, and motivations for participation, and preferred features and functionalities were addressed.</p> <p>Further refinements will be made based on continued feedback from the pilot cities in the second iteration of co-design (scheduled for M22-M36). The aim is to have an operational NSM page for each city by the end of the project, populated with climate stories that contribute to more inclusive and resilient urban futures.</p>			

This report presents the early stages of NSM’s development, highlighting its potential to raise awareness about climate change and drive meaningful engagement in urban climate action.

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Executive summary

Deliverable 6.6 outlines the first set of user and data requirements for the development of Neutrality Story Maps (NSM) – a key performance indicator (KPI) for the UP2030 project. NSM is conceptualised as a communication and engagement platform aimed at raising awareness and fostering citizen and policymaker collaboration on climate neutrality initiatives in urban environments. Using digital storytelling, NSM enables individuals to share their experiences, issues, hopes, and needs regarding climate and sustainability, while allowing cities to communicate scientific data and information about pilot-specific climate challenges and actions in an accessible narrative format. Besides empowering citizens to communicate their lived experience and vision for the future and allowing cities to raise awareness and engage citizens in climate neutrality initiatives, NSM supports cities in achieving spatial justice through informed urban planning and governance.

In practical terms, NSM provides a platform for two-way communication, where users can visualise climate data and share local stories in a map-based, multimedia format, including pictures, text, audio, and video. For policy- and decision-makers, NSM is especially useful for identifying areas of concern to anticipate problems and scope future resilience strategies. It allows them to gain direct insight into the experiences of citizens, ensuring that future urban planning initiatives are grounded in the realities faced by communities. Moreover, by communicating their pilot-specific climate-related vision and initiatives in an approachable format, cities can engage members of the public that do not feel concerned with climate change. For citizens, NSM offers a space to share stories about how climate change impacts their daily life in their city, what they wish would change, and what lifestyle changes they already adopted. Besides providing policy- and decision-makers with valuable qualitative data, these stories could inspire others to engage with climate neutrality initiatives and/or adopt environmentally friendly habits. Therefore, the NSM approach promotes social learning (Adelle et al., 2022) and helps policymakers avoid reproducing injustices (Wiebe, 2019).

The development of NSM within UP2030 is being conducted through a co-creative process led by the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) in collaboration with city representatives and citizens, with the technical implementation of the platform carried out by the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH). A crucial feature of NSM is its adaptability, as the exact design and functionality will vary based on the needs and preferences of the 10 pilot cities. Two rounds of development were planned to (1) co-design a first version of the website platform and (2) refine it and populate it with the climate stories. The first round, from M14 to M18, involved group interviews with the cities of Thessaloniki, Budapest, and Muenster in M16. The interviews aimed to explore how cities plan to align NSM with their pilot-specific vision, and to identify their motivation and barriers to use such a tool. The interviews were complemented by a workshop at the Cities Knowledge Exchange Event in Rotterdam in M18 and a post-workshop survey with all pilot cities to gather the first set of user requirements. This deliverable presents the results of the first round of co-creation with the cities, developing into a first version of the NSM platform, available here: [NSM Platform](#).

The next stage of development will begin in M22, where the platform will undergo further refinement based on the second round of co-design. Since having a NSM for each city is a KPI in the project, this process will ensure that each pilot city's NSM is fully tailored to its needs and ready for use by M36 (D6.7 - Neutrality Story Maps for the pilot cities 2). The platform will remain available to use for at least one

year after the project concludes. However, if a city wishes to continue using the platform beyond that time and requires specific updates, they can establish a contract with CERTH outlining their needs.

Ultimately, NSM will serve as a vital platform for engaging citizens and policymakers alike, creating a bridge between local communities and governance, and promoting collaborative efforts towards climate neutrality.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 Project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the Work Package structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with the work of the Engagement and Visioning Task Force (Mapping for Change (MfC), TSPA, I-Catalist (ICA), Resilient Cities Network (RCities)) and WP4 led by RCities. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
D2.5 Report on vision co-design methodology and its application for pilot shared visions	D3.9 Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice 2 D5.3 UP2030 service platform D6.5 Report on Dissemination and Communication actions and their impact 3
Mil. 6 Cities run second workshop on vision Mil. 11 Major city twinning “knowledge exchange” event	Mil. 13 All cities have at least one successful prototype

The target groups for this deliverable are policy and decision-makers, such as city representatives and urban planners, civil society organisations, and the ordinary citizens affected by climate change and the initiatives put in place by the cities to tackle it. The main beneficiaries of this content are stakeholders interested in tools for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice, such as the NSM platform. The VUB and CERTH aim to have an NSM for every city by the end of the project, which is a project KPI. However, as will be explained in this document, each NSM will be tailored to the needs and preferred level of engagement on the platform of each city. Therefore, different NSMs will reach completion at varying stages depending on the complexity of and number of features requested by each city. Beyond the publication of the document, the content will be socialised through interactive storytelling within the NSMs. The digital stories that will be created by city representatives and citizens and shown on the NSM platform will be publicly available, ensuring engagement at both the city and citizen levels.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
CERTH	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas
CMS	Content Management System
D	Deliverable
DSM	Digital Story Mapping
DST	Digital Storytelling
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
ICA	I-Catalist
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MDAT	Major Development Agency Thessaloniki
MfC	Mapping for Change
NSM	Neutrality Story Maps
RCities	Resilient Cities Network
T	Task
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package
UI	User Interface
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This deliverable report is part of WP6, Task (T) 6.2 - Dissemination and communication actions (M1-M36). As part of T6.2, the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) together with the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH) (the VUB's technical partner for the development of this tool), will develop Neutrality Story Maps (NSM) for the pilot cities. The methodology for digital storytelling (DST) using maps is being developed entirely within UP2030 by the VUB in a co-creative process with citizens and policymakers to foster tool ownership in each pilot city and to develop a website platform that is accessible, user friendly, and engaging. This methodology falls under the toolkit for behavioural change and deep engagement to inform planning and design with regards to citizen perceptions, preferences, and values that shape their sense of place (i.e., development of place identity). VUB is developing this methodology as part of T3.4 - Tools and approaches for promoting inclusive participation and spatial justice (M1-M36).

The collection of user and data requirements for the development of NSM were set up through different data-gathering activities. This present document describes how the first set of user requirements was gathered for the development of NSM, collected by the VUB and CERTH between M14 and M18 of the project.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: Description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure, and of the NSM concept and related storytelling/narrative methods.
- ❖ Section 2 – Methodology: User Requirement Analysis: Outline of the methodology used for the user requirement analysis for NSM. The different steps of this methodology and the corresponding data gathering and reporting techniques are explained with an overview of already implemented steps.
- ❖ Section 3 – Results: First set of user requirements that was generated from the data collected during different co-design activities, and then prioritised.
- ❖ Section 4 – Timeline for future activities: Summary of future co-design activities for the second part of the development of the NSM – D6.7 (Neutrality Story Maps for the Pilot Cities 2) starting M22.
- ❖ Section 5 – Conclusion: Main outcomes of the first round of co-design.

Section 6 –

- ❖ References
- ❖ Section 7 – Annex

1.3 [Neutrality Story Maps](#)

NSM is a mobile-friendly web platform that (1) allows cities to raise awareness about climate change by communicating climate-related challenges and initiatives put in place to tackle them and (2) empowers citizens to express their interests and hopes for their future city, especially in relation to their lived experience with climate change. NSM is versatile and adaptable, not limited to a fixed format. The platform offers various modes of DST that enable cities to share data or climate stories while allowing citizens to contribute through multimedia narrative formats. These contributions can include text-based stories, annotated maps that highlight personal experiences with climate impacts, or even multimedia entries combining audio and images (de Jager et al., 2017). For NSM, the diversity of formats offers cities the flexibility to engage with different stakeholder groups and empower citizens, especially marginalised ones, to express their concerns and hopes regarding the future of their cities. Starting from the idea that everyone is inherently creative, the platform’s adaptability is key to ensuring that storyteller citizens and policymakers are provided tools, templates, tips, and tricks – but above all; freedom – to shape their climate stories on the NSM platform in a way that is completely their own and reflects their living world.

1.3.1 [Theoretical Background](#)

DST is a narrative method that refers to a brief audio-visual clip lasting between two to five minutes, which integrates photographs, text, voice-over narration, video and additional audio elements (Lambert, 2012). NSM incorporates DST with Digital Story Mapping (DSM), a method for uncovering and creating meaning and knowledge through mapping the lived and embodied experience of a space on a digital map (Berendsen et al., 2018; Özyeşilpınar & Beltran, 2022). These methods are rooted in participatory and action-based approaches and provide a way to communicate scientific and complex information in an accessible and compelling format, and to make sense of lived experiences by narrating (personal) stories. They are suitable for participatory research with a flat hierarchy that aims to do research “with” rather than “on” participants, therefore considering them as equally valuable contributors (Lambert, 2012). DST was initially used for community development, education, artistic pursuits, and therapeutic practices, and has more recently been repurposed as a method for arts-based research used to uplift marginalised voices (de Jager et al., 2017). By highlighting the importance of meaning-making, storytelling, and questioning overarching uniform truth assertions, DST and DSM align interpretive, qualitative, and emancipatory research like feminist and critical theory with Indigenous research methodologies (Kovach, 2015).

Furthermore, stories that are not merely crafted for entertainment, or in other words, ‘serious’ storytelling, possess the transformative power to serve as radical instruments for advancing social and environmental justice (Wiebe, 2019; Lugmayr et al., 2017). By ‘storying’ the lived and embodied experience of marginalised groups with climate change and translating it into actionable knowledge that would otherwise be unharnessed, this method allows room for counter-narratives. It disrupts prevailing imaginaries and hegemonic political discourses that are often regarded as common sense and emancipates bounded imaginaries to strive towards alternative futures (de Jager et al., 2017; Escobar, 2023). In other words, DST and DSM foster possible decolonial and postcolonial approaches to planning and development

by acknowledging and deepening the understanding of traditional, situated, and implicit local knowledge, which is derived from diverse, context-based, and often intangible experiences of place and space (Constant & Roberts, 2017; Amorim-Maia et al., 2022; Özyeşilpınar & Beltran, 2022).

1.3.2 Application in UP2030

In the context of UP2030, NSM is envisioned as a platform that supports the socio-technical transitions necessary for cities to achieve their climate neutrality goals. NSM will be used to promote social learning, foster inclusive participation, and help cities adapt to the urban ramifications of climate change in a way that prioritises spatial justice and urban resilience (Pelling, 2010). Each of the 10 UP2030 pilot cities will have its own tailored NSM page, designed through a co-design approach that encourages tool ownership at the local level.

NSM in UP2030 will be designed to serve several key functions:

- Awareness raising: Cities can use their dedicated NSM page to communicate complex climate data in a more accessible and emotionally engaging way. They can promote city-level initiatives that aim to tackle their pilot-specific climate challenges, engage and mobilise citizens and other relevant stakeholders in climate neutrality city initiatives, and stimulate inclusive dialogue between society, policymakers, scientists, and urban planners.
- Citizen empowerment: NSM provides a platform for marginalised voices to share their experiences and perspectives on climate change, creating a rich tapestry of narratives that inform and humanise urban adaptation planning. Consequently, using NSM, citizens can express and share from a first-person perspective the issues they encounter, the concerns they have, the hopes they foster, and the needs they look to be addressed regarding climate and sustainability transitions in their city. Such narratives can prompt tacit knowledge about climate impacts and adaptation, which is often overlooked in scientific assessments but crucial for developing locally relevant solutions geared towards a just transition built around spatial justice and urban resilience (Bremer et al., 2017). By doing so, citizens can influence local climate adaptation strategies and policy decisions.
- Social learning: When applied in a governance context, NSM serves as a mechanism to promote social learning. Shifting away from purely positivist and data-driven approaches to policymaking towards a method that values practical knowledge. Incorporating moral and political judgment derived from lived experience and intuition, leads to a better understanding of complex policy problems such as climate change. This new understanding then becomes integrated into broader social groups and evolves through social interactions therefore encouraging the development of pro-environmental habits (Silberberg et al., 2013; Adelle et al., 2022). By centring the lived experience of citizens for other citizens to be inspired by, NSM serves as a learning tool for citizens that expands their knowledge on climate neutrality issues in a relatable format which will foster pro-environmental behaviours, intentions, and attitudes.

By capturing citizens' narratives about their personal experience of climate change, NSM supports cities in forecasting how the urban ramifications of climate change will worsen without action allowing them to better scope future resilience and how to achieve it, in a way that avoids the perpetuation of climate and spatial injustices (Pelling, 2010; Fraser, 2013). As such, NSM promotes planning approaches that prioritise

the use-value over the exchange-value of the city, emphasizing the city's role in meeting the social, cultural, and environmental needs of its inhabitants rather than focusing on its commodification for economic gain. Use-value refers to the value derived from the city's capacity to serve as a lived space that fosters well-being, community, and inclusivity, while exchange-value relates to the monetary worth of urban spaces in real estate markets, often driving gentrification and exclusion. By prioritising use-value, NSM supports planning practices that seek to enhance the quality of life for all citizens, particularly marginalised groups, making it a suitable method for anticipatory governance (Lefebvre, 1967; Floyd et al., 2016).

Additionally, involving communities in designing or planning their urban environment to be more adapted to climate change, or in other words 'placemaking', cultivates a sense of place among community members, enhancing their stewardship and responsibility for their neighbourhood or area (Ellery & Ellery, 2019). This, in turn, encourages the development of environmentally conscious habits and long-term behavioural changes (Silberberg et al., 2013).

As having a dedicated NSM for each of the 10 pilot cities is a key performance indicator (KPI) of the project, the platform is being developed through different co-design activities to tailor each NSM to the pilot-specific needs and aspirations. The co-creative approach is in line with the inclusive participation focus of UP2030 and aims to maximise the use value of the platform by providing an innovative, user-friendly, and accessible platform that reduces the digital divide while delivering actionable insights and fostering climate resilience. This methodology will be explained in detail in the following sections.

2 Methodology

Successful digital tools begin with an understanding of the needs and requirements of the users. Therefore, in accordance with the inclusive participation approach of UP2030, the VUB is co-designing NSM to develop an innovative platform that will respond to user needs and expectations. The exact design of NSM is not fixed; however, certain key characteristics are already established. NSM must allow users from different technical, social, and professional backgrounds to create digital stories geo-tagged on a map. Therefore, the platform needs to be accessible, user friendly, and incorporating different modes of narration to accommodate diverse storytelling approaches. These features aim to empower people and provide a digital platform that supports cities in the socio-technical transitions required to achieve their climate neutrality goals.

To ensure that each city's NSM is tailored to its specific context and needs, it was necessary to first collect user requirements. The development of the platform is divided in two rounds of co-design, with the first iteration spanning from M14 to M21 and the second round scheduled to start in M22 until M36. Since the methodology of digital storytelling using maps is being developed within UP2030, the user requirements had to be collected from scratch. Requirements are descriptions of an intended product that outline its expected functions and performance criteria, such as effectiveness, efficiency, satisfaction, accessibility, user experience, and avoidance of harm from use (Bevan et al., 2018). Understanding user requirements is critical for the success of a co-design project and maximising the impact of the product being developed.

The process of user requirements analysis is structured along four steps: 1) information gathering, 2) user needs identification, 3) envisioning and evaluation, and 4) requirements specification (Maguire & Bevan, 2002). An initial set of user requirements was generated through a mixed-method approach using various research methodologies such as surveys, interviews, and workshops with various stakeholders from M14 to M18. The collected requirements served as input for the design and the development of the first coded version of the platform.

One of the main challenges of co-design is addressing complex situations where the different needs of stakeholders must be reconciled in a short timeframe. This timeframe will be explained in further detail in Section 2.1. To mitigate this challenge, appropriate data collection methods had to be implemented at each step of co-design to gather an initial set of user requirements from a variety of stakeholders from the ten UP2030 pilot cities. The information gathering phase to develop the initial set of user requirements was conducted in M15. The first step was to present the NSM concept to the cities during the cities cluster meetings that were organised by the engagement and visioning task force (MfC, TSPA, ICA, VUB, CERTH, UIC, led by RCities) with 10 pilot cities divided in three clusters (see Table 2). Surveys were distributed after the meetings to identify the potential users of the tool, along with their barriers to participation and motivation to use the tool.

User needs identification, based on the identified users, was achieved in M16 through interviews with three forerunner pilot cities that chose to participate in the first round of co-design: Budapest, Thessaloniki, and Muenster. Based on the data collected in this first phase of co-design, CERTH developed mock-ups for the NSM platform in M17 for the envisioning and evaluation phase of the user analysis process. The mock-ups were then presented in a workshop at the Cities Knowledge Exchange event in Rotterdam in M18. The workshop served to gather feedback on the first visualisation of the tool from the pilot cities in attendance and to brainstorm together about new ideas, additional features, and areas for improvement for the second iteration of co-design. The requirements specification phase then started in

M18 and M19 to prioritise user requirements that will be included in the first coded version of the tool following the MoSCoW (Must have, Should have, Could have, Won't have) method, a method for prioritizing user requirements (more details in Section 3.1.4), and setting criteria for future co-design activities planned for the second iteration of co-design.

2.1 Challenges and Deviations

Due to staff changes at the VUB, the development of the NSM website was delayed for six months. To mitigate the impacts of this delay, the user requirements data gathering activities were adapted. The co-design workshops that were initially planned were replaced by group interviews in M16 to identify user needs for the tool based on which the mock-ups were developed by CERTH in M17. The reason behind this decision is that group interviews allow to get more specific and targeted answers about users' needs from the cities and are less time consuming in terms of organisation and participants recruitment. Also, the intended concept of the tool has changed. The concept was initially inspired by the ArcGIS StoryMaps tool, specifically the [Milan story map example](#). After discussing it with CERTH, the UP2030 coordination team, the engagement and visioning taskforce, and the cities, it was collectively decided that NSMs are not only going to be a webpage that showcases the success stories of each pilot city. Instead, a more comprehensive approach to citizen engagement will be embraced, where the platform will not only enable cities to share their digital stories but also empower citizens to express their concerns and hopes in a narrative format through the platform. Depending on which other communication and citizen engagement channels the pilot cities use, the cities decided which level of engagement on the platform suits their planned activities within UP2030 the best and whether they want to use it as a one-way or two-way communication channel that aims to raise awareness while engaging citizens in climate neutrality initiatives. There have been no further deviations, and the status of the tool is back on track and up to date. A timeline for future activities is provided at the end of this report that details how NSM will be delivered on time by the end of the project.

2.2 Data Gathering Activities

The data gathering activities for the user requirement analysis took place between M15 and M18, to collect and generate a set of requirements based on which the first version of the tool was developed. This marks the first round of co-design. These data gathering and co-design activities aimed to find out who the users would be and what would encourage them to use the platform/tool (motivation), what would discourage them (barriers), and what they would like to use the tool for and in which context, as well as co-define features that the users would deem useful to be included in the tool. The data was collected using a variety of quantitative and qualitative research methods such as surveys, interviews, and workshops that were chosen according to the data required for each step of user analysis (see Table 1). Each co-design activity will be detailed below.

Table 1: Timeline of data gathering activities for the first round of co-design.

Activity	Month						
	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Survey	█	█					
Group Interviews		█					
Rotterdam Workshop				█			
Post-Workshop Survey				█			
Preparatory Meetings 2 nd round of co-design					█	█	█

2.2.1 UP2030 Cities Cluster Meetings

During M15, the engagement and visioning task force organised three meetings with clusters of pilot cities:

Table 2: City clusters for NSM concept presentation meetings (M15)

06/04/2024 with Cluster 1 led by MfC	07/03/2024 with Cluster 2 led by RCities	12/03/2024 with Cluster 3 led by ICA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Muenster • Lisbon • Belfast 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Milan • Rotterdam • Thessaloniki • Istanbul 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zagreb • Budapest • Granollers

These one-hour meetings were organised by members of the engagement and visioning task force (that were also city liaisons) to allow the VUB and CERTH to present the NSM concept to the pilot cities and gauge their interest in which level of the co-design process of the tool they would be willing and available to be involved in, and for Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI), an UP2030 consortium partner to present their Green Economy Model and Climate Prio tools to the cities (UP2030, 2022). The presentation was designed in a way that allows for interaction and fruitful discussion between the VUB, CERTH, and the cities in attendance. Also, the NSM presentation was complemented with a short Mentimeter poll that encouraged cities to discuss how they saw NSM aligning with their pilot-specific communication and engagement strategies. After these meetings, Google Forms surveys were distributed via email to gather initial information and plan for the next steps in the co-design process. Surveys were used as a relatively

quick and effective method for obtaining insights from a large sample of potential users (Maguire & Bevan, 2002). They gathered information about the various communication channels cities use to engage with citizens around climate neutrality initiatives, their views on NSM aligning with planned activities, the profile of citizens they aim to engage, expected barriers and motivations for participation using the tool, and the preferred round of co-design in which the cities want to participate (see Annex 1: Survey Results).

2.2.2 Group Interviews

The second step of user requirement collection after gathering some general information about the potential users and context of use, is to identify specific user needs (Maguire & Bevan, 2002). Group interviews are efficient for this objective as they allow researchers to obtain more in-depth information about the needs of multiple users and are therefore a suitable method for this second step of user requirement analysis (Pacheco et al., 2018). The VUB scheduled a first exchange in M16 with the cities that decided to participate in the first round of co-design – i.e., Muenster, Budapest, and Thessaloniki. This was a one-on-one meeting with each city that occurred one time. During these meetings, the tool was presented to the cities for the second time with a preliminary planning for the co-design process. It was decided together with the cities to organise a group interview with the relevant stakeholders in M16 to gather user needs that would generate the first set of user requirements based on which the mock-ups of NSM would be developed by CERTH in M17. Besides identifying user needs, motivation, and barriers to using the tool and how to overcome them together with the relevant stakeholders, the goal of these interviews was to brainstorm with the cities and identify synergies between NSM and their vision and work plan for UP2030. The main themes that would be discussed during the interviews were communicated to the participants prior to the scheduled date to allow them to discuss internally and prepare some material for discussion during the interview (see Annex 2: Interview Questionnaire). Consent forms were distributed prior to the interview, and participants were asked to return their signed forms before the interview took place (see Annex 4: Consent Forms). Those who could not sign and send the consent forms beforehand were asked to provide consent orally at the start of the interview. The interviews were conducted online on MS Teams, lasted around 90 minutes, and were recorded, transcribed, and analysed to generate a first set of user requirements for these three cities. The specific user requirements for each of the interviews will be detailed in Section 3 of this report.

1. Budapest 24/04/2024

The group interview with Budapest was conducted on the 23rd of April, 2024. The participants from the City of Budapest in this interview were the Deputy Head of The Department for Environment and Climate, and an Active and Micromobility Expert at the Department for Environment and Climate. Furthermore, one participant from GGGI, the liaison for Budapest was present in the interview but only as an observer. The language of the interview was English and Milutin Djuraskovic from the VUB conducted the interview.

The representatives for the city of Budapest explained that they were interested in using NSM as a two-way communication stream to gather data from citizens and understand their needs while also informing them about climate neutrality related developments in their city. The city envisions using this tool to collect data on which areas are sensitive or most vulnerable to extreme weather conditions and precipitation events, identifying problems like conflicts between pedestrians, cars, or cyclists, as well as

gather the public's interests for future urban planning and design. This collected data based on the lived experience of citizens would help them to anticipate urban floods, dry periods, and plan better rainwater collection and water management. Moreover, Budapest expressed their vision of aligning NSM with the [Healthy Streets®](#) approach adopted within their pilot. To achieve the goal of increasing access to a healthy environment, Budapest's leadership committed in 2021 to implementing the Healthy Streets® approach. This approach is structured around 10 indicators: everyone feels welcome, easy to cross, shade and shelter, places to stop and rest, not too noisy, people choose to walk and cycle, people feel safe, things to see and do, people feel relaxed, and clean air.

The digital stories submitted by the citizens on the NSM platform could be analysed, using analytics such as key word and sentiment analysis to provide valuable insights to urban designers and policymakers so they can implement changes based on this newly harnessed knowledge, and by re-evaluating, they can gauge progress and identify areas needing further focus. As a result of this approach, Budapest expects the first users of the platform to be young citizens and professionals who are informed about the risks of climate change and that adopt environmentally friendly habits and routine. However, they hope to engage other citizen profiles and to onboard districts to use this tool or similar ones for community engagement. Nevertheless, they expect this to be a challenge due to a lack of digital skills and capacity within the districts caused by underfinancing, as well as a disconnect between the districts.

After discussing the city's preferred level of engagement, the potential users, and their motivation and barriers to using the platform, the preferred format of the stories was discussed. Budapest was keen on an interactive story creation template where users can use pictures and short text, but not so keen on using voice notes. The stories will then be presented on a timeline and on a map with the possibility of grouping them in threads revolving around certain pre-defined themes and tags linked to the Healthy Streets indicators, and to various climate neutrality initiatives. The users should be able to interact with the stories using likes and comments, and to also share the stories on social media for a wider reach that would help foster social learning and engage more citizens in climate neutrality initiatives.

Budapest also stated that they aim to introduce the tool within the knowledge centre that they plan to establish by the end of the project. They intend to introduce the tool with the engaged district that already has some capacity but may instead opt to involve NGOs or consulting firms. They hope that by providing tools to districts they will encourage them to develop internal capacities for feedback gathering, reducing reliance on costly external consultants which is in line with the UP-Skilling part of the 5UPs methodology that is being developed within the UP2030 project. Ultimately their goal is to foster increased district engagement in projects that focus on community involvement. Should the tool become popular and used for different purposes, they expressed their interest in continuing to use it after the end of the project.

2. Thessaloniki 25/04/2024

The group interview with Thessaloniki was conducted on the 25th of April, 2024. The participants from the city of Thessaloniki included one participant from the Department of Operational Planning and Monitoring of Development Projects in the municipality, one participant from the Major Development Agency Thessaloniki (MDAT), which supports the municipality in the implementation of UP2030, and seven citizens. The interview was led in Greek by Nick Pantelidis from CERTH and provided crucial insights on the needs of different profiles of users.

Thessaloniki wants to use NSM primarily in the Dioikitirio area. Dioikitirio is a neighbourhood in Thessaloniki that the municipality aims to transform into a sustainable, thriving & climate-resilient community, with a mix of residential, commercial and recreational spaces. The goal is to use NSM as a participatory tool, empowering citizens to actively engage in the decision-making process and shape the future of their neighbourhood.

However, it was noted that in Greek society, the traditional methods of communication, such as posters, flyers or more direct ways such as phone calls and in-person interactions, remain the most effective ways to engage citizens. While these methods are effective, they tend to reach only those who are already engaged in community activities and are aware of environmental issues. On the other hand, digital means of communication, such as social media posts, have proven to be more effective in attracting new participants. Since the goal of the municipality is to attract as many citizens as possible in the decision-making process, they see potential in leveraging NSM to achieve this broader engagement.

Regarding the users of the tool, although the municipality aims to include everyone, certain groups may be more likely to become the first users. For example, in the case of the Dioikitirio neighbourhood, workshops with elderly people have been particularly successful. However, for NSM, which is a digital tool, students were suggested as the ideal initial target group. This is because they are not only digitally literate and more comfortable with new technologies, but they are also exposed to environmental topics as part of their school curriculum. This makes them more likely to engage with the tool, which could also be incorporated into a school course and promoted through it.

Moreover, it was noted that collaborative design is still not common in Greek society. Nonetheless, the municipality is working to establish it, believing that it will be beneficial both for the municipality and the citizens. Another reason that they believe the citizens are not eager to participate is that in the previous years, the municipality was not promoting the bi-directional communication with the citizens. However, nowadays, more and more citizens care about their communities and they want to be part of the decision-making process when it comes to their neighbourhood. It was highlighted that the municipality should demonstrate that they value and consider citizens' input when they make decisions; otherwise, people may become disappointed and stop participating. Additionally, it was emphasised how important it is for the municipality not only to promote the NSM as a tool but also to actively incorporate it into their communication strategies with citizens.

Thessaloniki decided to use the tool with the collaborative approach, crowdsourcing stories from citizens. The tool will be used as a standardised way for the citizens to communicate with the municipality and vice versa, encouraging bottom-up dialogue. Since climate neutrality concerns all citizens, the tool should be inclusive, user friendly, and accessible to an average citizen. The training of the users was also mentioned as important for the users to know how to use the tool properly. This way, everyone can use the tool and contribute to discussions on how their neighbourhood can become more human-friendly and sustainable.

Additionally, the tool should provide timely and accurate information. It should be used by the municipality as a hub for everything related to climate neutrality. This way, even citizens who are currently uninterested in certain issues or plans can find relevant information in the future.

When it comes to the more technical characteristics of the tool, Thessaloniki emphasised the need for stories to include images and videos, reflecting the media preferences of younger users on other platforms. They recommended offering ready-made templates for stories, limiting text length, and allowing multiple tags per story. While they found the idea of commenting quite useful, they suggested

setting limits on comment length and the number of comments a user can make on a story. They also recommended imposing a general cap on the number of comments a user can post within a specific timeframe. For threads, they advised keeping descriptions brief and limiting the number of stories per thread. They supported the idea of accessing stories from other cities to take inspiration but suggested not displaying them in the main timeline. Regarding analytics, they liked the concept but had no additional suggestions.

3. Muenster 30/04/2024

The group interview with Muenster took place on the 30th of April 2024 with one participant from the municipality, whose work focuses on the KlimaTraining and citizen participation. The Muenster KlimaTraining occurs twice a year, with approximately 50 participants including citizens and public servants divided into small groups of about five. These groups are guided by volunteer climate trainers who help participants develop and integrate climate-friendly habits into their daily lives. Participants can test and incorporate sustainable products and services provided by local companies and organisations, covering areas like housing, energy, mobility, consumption, and nutrition. The offers are regularly updated, with new initiatives such as climate communication in development. Due to unforeseen circumstances, the group interview turned to a semi-structured interview. Nevertheless, Muenster provided some answers to the topic list via email and the interview yielded valuable information on the potential ways NSM could be used to multiply the impact of the KlimaTraining in Muenster. The interview was conducted in English by Milutin Djuraskovic from the VUB.

During previous exchanges with Muenster and the group interview, it was envisaged that NSM must be linked to Muenster's KlimaTraining. It was reiterated in the interview that the tool could be used to market the KlimaTraining and display its positive outcomes and inspire more citizens to participate in the KlimaTraining. The digital stories submitted on the NSM platform could reveal the trigger moment that made citizens spark a change in their behaviour. Moreover, the tool could possibly be used to communicate climate related information in a way that does not scare people away and help the city deal with climate deniers, therefore raising awareness through stories as suggested by Muenster. NSM in Muenster through the approach of citizen-to-citizen storytelling could be used as an informative tool that is expected to be used by citizens who already have experience with climate-related issues, such as the participants and trainers of the KlimaTraining. However, the city hopes to also engage citizens with the largest carbon footprint.

Nevertheless, in Muenster, a pilot-specific barrier to use the tool has been communicated that goes beyond the usual language barrier, and the lack of digital skills when using digital tools. Here, the municipality and politicians formally decided before NSM were presented to Muenster to use another citizen participation tool; the [Beteiligung NRW](#) tool. The participation portal is designed for citizens and public bodies. Politicians or administrators post discussion topics and surveys, allowing registered users to share their opinions, ideas, and suggestions within a set timeframe, either through written contributions or video messages. After the participation period ends, the administration provides a final summary, and the entire process is archived for future reference. Therefore, according to Muenster, NSM could only be used if there is a way to integrate it with the Beteiligung NRW tool. As having NSM for each pilot city is a KPI in the project, the VUB and CERTH will continue to engage with Muenster to try and find a way for Muenster to have a NSM by the end of the project.

After discussing the barriers and motivation of the city to use the tool, the preferred format of the digital story was discussed. Muenster is keen on including videos in the interactive story creation template that show the image of the storyteller with a short text. The stories can be presented on a timeline and on a map with the possibility of clustering them along certain categories and tags defined by the citizens. The users should also be able to interact with the stories using likes, comments, but also to report the stories that include inappropriate content such as problematic language and/or audio-visual content.

2.2.3 Cities Knowledge Exchange Rotterdam Workshop

In M17, CERTH developed six mock-ups of the NSM platform based on the user requirements generated from the data gathered in the group interviews. The mock-ups were then presented in a workshop during the Cities Knowledge Exchange event in Rotterdam in M18. This data-gathering activity falls within the envisioning and evaluation stage of the user requirements analysis methodology (Maguire & Bevan, 2002). The goal of the workshop was to present the mock-ups to all cities and partners in attendance and gather feedback on this first visualisation of the tool. The workshop lasted around 90 minutes and was structured in three parts. First, the VUB presented the concept of the tool, and the user requirements derived from the group interviews held with Muenster, Budapest, and Thessaloniki, and CERTH presented the tool's workflow on Figma, the software they used to create the mock-ups. CERTH went through the mock-ups one by one to show how users can create stories, what type of media and templates they can use, how the stories will be presented on a timeline and a map, how the stories will be gathered in threads based on tags and themes, and the resources page where cities can upload educational material and various news and updates. The second part of the workshop focused on identifying positive aspects of the mock-ups presented and areas for improvement. This was done with the help of a Mentimeter poll. Each mock-up was shown on the main screen while the Mentimeter poll was shown simultaneously on a side screen. The participants were asked to connect to the Mentimeter poll using their smartphone or laptop and to submit their answers regarding positive aspects and new ideas for improvement for each mock-up. The last part of the workshop was a plenary discussion where the VUB and CERTH engaged participants in a discussion to expand on their suggestions provided on the Mentimeter poll.

Figure 1: Neutrality Story Maps workshop at the Cities Knowledge Exchange Event in Rotterdam (M18)

The key takeaways from this activity were that first, the feedback received during the workshop revealed that the platform looked easy to use, intuitive in nature, and simple in design. Some cities pointed out that the platform may be demanding in terms of managing and moderating. Therefore, the feature that allows cities to disable comments and any interaction with the stories will be added. This way, the cities can minimise the effort required from their side in terms of monitoring the comments section of the platform. Two pilot cities stated that in their specific case there is no clear connection with the NSM tool within their work plan and therefore that they chose to opt out of participating in its development. The VUB assured them that there are ways to align the tool with the city's overall goals and that they will continue to tailor each NSM to the cities' needs. In addition, since having a NSM for each city is a KPI in this project, the VUB explained that if these two pilot cities decide not to have a NSM for their pilot by the end of the project, then they must provide an official statement that justifies why that is the case to coordination.

Lastly, three options for how cities could use the NSM platform were identified (see Table 3):

1. Crowdsourcing stories from citizens – collecting stories from citizens to assist cities in anticipating problems, evaluating initiatives, gathering interests for future urban planning and restoration, harnessing citizen sentiment based on the lived experience and future vision of citizens as originally designed by the VUB & CERTH.

2. Cities as the storyteller – cities populate the web platform with curated stories/threads geotagged on a map to communicate the impact of their initiatives and success stories.
3. One separate webpage co-created with the city – data and maps intended to communicate the risks being addressed by the pilot project in a narrative format and expressed in an accessible way, written from the perspective of a one-story/character persona.

2.2.4 Post-Workshop Survey

After the Rotterdam workshop, a follow-up survey was distributed to all pilot cities to collect extra user requirements on the points that arose during the workshop. The survey aimed to determine how users should register to use the website, their preferred length and format for the digital story, how these stories are to be presented on the map, and what insights the cities hope to get from the stories so analytics can be embedded in their personal dashboard (see Annex 3: Post-Workshop Survey Report). The feedback gathered during the Rotterdam workshop and this follow-up survey provided CERTH with additional user requirements to include in the first coded version of NSM. The results of the different data gathering activities, and the first generated list of user requirements will be detailed in the results section below.

2.2.5 Preparatory Meetings for the 2nd Round of Co-Design

The VUB and CERTH organised online meetings with the pilot cities from M19 to M21 to prepare for the second iteration of co-design. The meetings served to (1) present NSM to the stakeholders that weren't involved in the first iteration of co-design and (2) discuss how they envision using the platform in their pilot to plan the second round of co-design activities and streamline them with the workshops scheduled for the action phase of the project. During the meetings, the concept of the NSM platform was presented to the attendees, especially to those who did not participate in the first round of co-design, along with the user requirements that were generated, and the mock-ups of the platform that were shown in the Rotterdam workshop. After presenting this information, the VUB and CERTH engaged in a brainstorming session with the representatives of the cities with the aim of defining how best to align the NSM platform with pilot-specific goals and vision, and choosing one or more out of the three options to use the platform that were defined in the Rotterdam workshop (see Section 2.2.3). The table below presents the preferred option to use the NSM platform by each of the 10 pilot cities.

Table 3: Chosen NSM option(s) per city

City	NSM Option 1: Crowdsourcing Stories from Citizens	NSM Option 2: The City Curating Stories	NSM Option 3: Co-Created Scrollytelling Webpage
Belfast		X	X
Budapest	X		
Granollers			X

Istanbul			X
Lisbon		X	
Milan			X
Muenster			X
Rotterdam		X	
Thessaloniki	X		
Zagreb		X	

Other insights from each of the pilot cities that emerged from this workshop included:

- Belfast will use NSM to capture citizens’ sentiment around climate related experiences in their pilot neighbourhoods and communicate it through personas based on conversations that they have planned with their citizens.
- Budapest plans to use NSM to learn about the experiences of citizens in their communities, and to crowdsource information about what citizens want and need in their area. This is still to be confirmed, and another brainstorming session is planned with the Budapest team in M21.
- Granollers aims to disseminate information about their work within UP2030, and key projects which have already been produced around green zones and sustainable mobility in an accessible multimedia format.
- Istanbul aims to use the platform to raise awareness around climate change and showcase the initiatives put in place in their pilot to tackle their pilot-specific risks. They also aim to advertise public events and educational material on the platform.
- Lisbon wants to present key elements of each of their four pilots: (1) Market about inclusion, (2) Rugby club, (3) LNEC research centre, (4) Library. The stories will be told by pilot ambassadors.
- Milan will present complex data about the urban services ecosystem in their pilot in a form of a digital story with a multilayered map on the platform.
- Muenster is contemplating using NSM to advertise their Klimatraining and inspire more people to implement lifestyle changes. This is still to be confirmed as Muenster is still not sure if they want to use the platform.
- Rotterdam will use NSM to showcase the lessons learnt from the BoTu neighbourhood through stories about the community, to share their successes for replicability in other neighbourhoods in Rotterdam and beyond.
- Thessaloniki wants to use the platform to create stories for their own use and announce relevant events and calls for action both by the city and citizens.
- Zagreb wants to try the platform with students in a school in their pilot.

Furthermore, during these meetings, the VUB and CERTH discussed with the cities how to streamline the second round of co-design activities with the action phase of UP2030. During these discussions, it was determined that a first version of each NSM for each pilot city would be achieved by M26, which is the deadline for the cities to present their first version of their prototype (Milestone 13: All cities have at least one successful prototype). For the cities that chose Option 3, this will be a first version of their NSM webpage coded by CERTH according to the preferences and content provided by the cities. For cities that chose Options 2 and 3, the first version of their NSM will be a first set of digital stories created on the platform by the cities and/or citizens, after getting the required training by the VUB and CERTH on how to use the platform. The preliminary timeline for the second iteration of co-design will be presented in Section 4 of this report.

3 Results

The first round of co-design was conducted between M14 and M18 (see section 2.2). In the initial phase, VUB conceptualised the NSM idea, while CERTH translated it into a description of the tool's structure and an initial list of user requirements.

In M16 VUB held group interviews with three cities, Budapest, Thessaloniki, and Muenster, to better understand their needs, how they intended to use NSM, collect user requirements and refine the existing ones. Following these interviews, the updated requirements were transformed into mock-ups, which were presented during a workshop at the Cities Knowledge Exchange meeting in Rotterdam (see section 2.2.3) in M18. The purpose of the workshop was to gather feedback from the participating cities and identify any additional user requirements, with the mock-ups serving as a basis for discussion.

After integrating the feedback from the Rotterdam workshop, the list of requirements was finalised and prioritised using the MoSCoW prioritisation technique (Clegg & Barker, 1994). Based on the priorities assigned to each requirement, CERTH began developing the tool in M18. The following sections cover NSM's tool concept, the initial user requirements, the insights gathered during the group interviews in the first co-design round, descriptions of the mock-ups (along with the mock-ups themselves), and a description of the tool as it has been developed so far, including screenshots of the actual tool.

3.1 User Requirements

One of the most important aspects when developing a new tool is the collection of user requirements. This involves clearly defining the structure of the tool, what users need the tool to accomplish, and how they want it to function and appear. Gathering all these requirements and taking them into account ensures the tool not only meets the user expectations but is also practical and effective in its intended use. Additionally, having a clear understanding of the tool's structure and initial user requirements is necessary for starting to design a tool.

To achieve this for NSM, feedback and user requirements were collected from all pilot cities through various data gathering activities. This process was essential for aligning the tool's design with actual user needs. The subsequent sections will detail the process of defining these requirements and outline the specific needs that emerged from the various meetings.

3.1.1 Tool Structure and Initial User Requirements

As the lead on the methodology development of NSM, the VUB developed an initial vision of the tool's design and functionality, while UP2030's commitment to citizen engagement in the pilot cities was guaranteed. To bring this vision to life, CERTH, the partner responsible for the technical implementation of the tool, held several meetings with the VUB to fully understand their expectations regarding the functionality and appearance of the tool. Based on the outcomes of these meetings, CERTH proposed an initial structure for the tool along with a preliminary set of user requirements considering technical feasibility. This proposal was then reviewed with the VUB and the partners from the Engagement and Visioning Taskforce, as well as the coordinators, and adjusted accordingly.

The agreed upon structure of the tool is described below. The core component of the tool is ‘stories’, which are posts that users can create. Each ‘story’ consists of multiple pages, and each page can contain text, image, video, audio, or a combination of these elements, such as text over an image or audio with an image. The option of adding maps will also be explored. A ‘story page’ occupies the entire screen (in both the desktop and mobile versions), with the pages changing with visually appealing transitions as the user scrolls through the story. All stories are geotagged so they can be displayed on a map. The creator of a ‘story’ can assign tags to their story. Tags are descriptive keywords related to the story’s content, like hashtags on social media. Additionally, users can add text-only comments to the stories, as well as ‘like’ stories, or ‘share’ them on social media platforms.

There are two main types of users: citizens and cities.

- Citizens can register on the platform and select one of the cities where the tool is available. They may need to provide proof of residency in the selected city if the city requires verification to confirm that users are residents of the area. Once registered, they can create new stories and report comments or stories for inappropriate content. If a story or comment receives more than a specified number of reports, it will be hidden until the city reviews it.
- Cities, on the other hand, have additional capabilities. They can create a customised list of tags for their city and initiate new threads. A thread is a topic that cities can create within the platform. It allows cities to organise and categorise content around specific themes or subjects. Each thread includes a description provided by the city that explains the purpose of the thread, and users can submit their stories related to that topic. Additionally, cities can create and upload resources, such as educational articles or videos, that will be available to citizens. They are responsible for moderating comments and stories. If, as per the different requirements for the NSM of each city, cities require users to verify that they live in the city, they will need to manually verify each new user.

Both citizens and cities can view a preview of all stories in a timeline and on a map, with the option to filter them based on various parameters. Finally, the tool will be mobile-friendly, include accessibility features for users with special needs, support translations in the languages of the cities involved in the project. Additionally, it will offer a dashboard for city administrators, providing tools for managing and customising the app, as well as offering analytics and statistics based on the specific needs and requests of each city.

3.1.2 [Group Interviews](#)

After deciding the structure of the tool, contact with the project’s cities was initiated to arrange interviews. The goal was to present the tool’s structure and gather insights on how each city plans to use it, assess if it meets their needs, and collect additional user requirements. For this first round of co-design, three cities, Budapest, Thessaloniki, and Muenster, agreed to participate.

Budapest

As discussed during the group interview with Budapest, outlined in section 2.2.2, the city expressed interest in using the tool as a two-way communication channel, both to collect data from citizens and to inform them about climate neutrality-related topics. Based on the discussion, the user requirements in Table 4 were identified.

Table 4: Requirements from the Budapest interview

Requirements
Users can use the platform without logging in, by simply providing their name
Posting on the platform could require obligatory demographic information such as age group, gender, and residency status. However, this process must be quick and user friendly to not discourage citizens from using the platform
Stories should contain images
Stories' text must be short
An interactive template for creating stories should be provided
No audio files in stories
Text or ready-made small images to overlay over images when creating a new story
Stories should include tags that have been predefined by the city to simplify the process for users
Filtered search and view of the stories
Map to 'pin' the stories
Threads must be available for submitting stories on specific topics/questions or images
Users should be able to share platform content on social media
Access to stories from other cities is not necessary
Analytics, such as sentiment and keyword analysis, could be useful

Thessaloniki

According to the group interview with Thessaloniki (see section 2.2.2), they want to use NSM as a participatory tool to engage citizens in decision-making on climate neutrality topics. The tool will also serve as a platform for the city to share information on climate neutrality and their related initiatives. The list of user requirements that were identified during the meeting is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Requirements from the Thessaloniki interview

Requirements
Support for images and videos in stories
Ready-made templates for creating new stories should be provided
Stories should not contain long text

Stories should have tags, with support for multiple tags per story
Threads dedicated to specific topics
No long descriptions for threads should be allowed
Limit on the number of stories allowed under each thread
Access to stories from other cities, but not displayed in the main timeline
Comments under stories, with a limit on the number of characters per comment
Restriction on the number of comments a user can make under a story and overall
Ability to 'like' stories
Analytics about the stories

Muenster

From the interview with Muenster (see section 2.2.2), it was concluded that Muenster intended to use the tool for two main purposes: enabling citizens to report their KlimaTraining progress and allowing the city to promote KlimaTraining and provide information on climate neutrality-related topics. This is still to be confirmed with Muenster. Based on the discussion, the list of requirements that is presented in Table 6 was identified.

Table 6: Requirements from the Muenster interview

Requirements
Stories should include videos
Interactive story creation template
Short text in the stories
Text prompts when creating a new story
Stories should have tags, with a predefined list available from the city, but citizens can also add their own
Filter stories based on their tags
Stories should be displayed in a timeline and on a map
Map to show the locations of the stories
Users can see stories from other cities, but this is not necessary

Share stories to social media
Threads around a specific topic
Ability to like stories
Comment under stories
Ability to report stories with inappropriate content
The application must be mobile-friendly

3.1.3 Additional user requirements from Rotterdam workshop

During the workshop in Rotterdam, the mock-ups of the NSM were presented to the cities and project partners in attendance. The primary purpose of this presentation was to gather feedback on this initial visualisation of the tool's user interface (UI). Since it was the first time showing the actual design, many comments and suggestions were received.

After a fruitful discussion with the attending partners and cities about the positive aspects of the tool, some concerns were raised by some cities about the moderation and translation of the tool's content. Regarding moderation, it was suggested that cities could use the planned reporting functionality where users can report inappropriate or irrelevant content. However, if they want more control over the content before it is published, an option can be added for reviewing each story before it goes public. Representatives from Zagreb also pointed out that from their experience the comment sections under stories could be misused by citizens to create conflicts and attack city representative personnel for malicious purposes, while the comments section is for providing constructive feedback and comments relevant to the stories. To address this, it was proposed giving cities the option to disable comments if necessary. Regarding translation, some partners noted that many cities have citizens who do not speak the local language, and suggested implementing automatic translation for user-generated content to ensure the platform is inclusive. Additionally, there was concern about who should have access to create content. Some cities proposed that only verified organisations, such as NGOs, be allowed to create content to prevent the upload of irrelevant material and reduce the need for moderation from the cities.

Several additional changes were proposed by cities and partners:

- It was suggested that the usernames of story creators should not be visible
- The ability to group stories by the creator's age was proposed. That means that the users should provide their age upon registering to the platform
- Users should have the option to follow a story to receive notifications about new comments or any other updates
- Adding thumbnails to thread previews was recommended to make them more distinguishable from the others

- Connecting resources with threads. This would ensure that all relevant information for a thread does not have to be included in the thread's description. Instead, a link to a resource could be provided, offering more detailed content like images, videos, and additional information
- To improve inclusiveness, every audio or video in stories should be accompanied by text subtitles, ensuring the content is accessible to hard of hearing users
- A forum feature was suggested to facilitate discussions on various topics among citizens
- Regarding the map of the platform, it was suggested to provide different basemaps, such as satellite view, and to allow cities to add custom layers to highlight parts of the city (e.g., green areas).
- Selecting a story pin on the map should display a popup with a preview of the story

3.1.4 Final requirements

Following the completion of all data-gathering activities, a comprehensive list of user requirements was compiled that derived from these processes. This final list is presented in Table 7. Each requirement has been assigned a priority level using the MoSCoW method (Clegg & Barker, 1994). The MoSCoW method is a popular prioritisation technique for managing requirements, in which requirements are categorised into four distinct levels of importance:

1. **Must Have:** Core features that are absolutely necessary for the product to function. These are the features that the product cannot launch without.
2. **Should Have:** Important features that add significant value to the product but are not critical to its basic functionality. These features should be included if possible but can be deferred till later if there are time constraints.
3. **Could Have:** These are 'nice-to-have' features that enhance the user experience but are not essential and have a lower impact in the final product. These features are the first to be deprioritised if the features from the previous two categories take more time than expected.
4. **Won't Have (at this time):** These are features that are intentionally excluded from the current version of the product. Some of these features might be considered for future updates, while others may not be implemented at all. If time and resources allow, certain features from this category might be added.

By categorising requirements with the MoSCoW method, project teams can ensure that they focus on delivering the most critical elements first, while keeping track of additional features that could be incorporated if time and resources permit.

In the case of NSM, while most of the requirements are important to at least some cities, they had to be prioritised first based on the input of the cities and how much they need each of them and second based on the available time. In this way, the focus was on implementing the core functionalities of the tool first, followed by additional features as time permits. Therefore, the requirements categorised as 'Must Have' are the essential features that define NSM and are important for the tool to work properly. These include key functionalities such as user registration on the platform, the ability to create stories, support for stories

to include images, videos, and text, ensuring the app is available in the various languages of the participating cities, etc.

The requirements with a ‘Should Have’ priority are those that complement the core features of NSM and enhance the overall functionality of the tool. While these features are important for delivering a good final product, they are not absolutely essential for the app’s initial operation. Examples include the ability to like, report, or share a story, as well as the option to have different basemaps for the map. The plan is to implement all the requirements in this priority category.

The requirements in the ‘Could Have’ category are requirements that will probably not be implemented mainly due to the time available. Therefore, if time permits, most of these requirements will be implemented as well. The reasons that these requirements are placed in this category are mainly a combination of lack of interest from most of the cities, functionalities that offer only a small additional benefit or do not significantly enhance the tool’s core functionality and complex functionalities that require a lot of time to implement.

A requirement in this category that is worth mentioning is the ability to comment on stories. In the initial conceptualisation of NSM, this feature was considered a crucial component. However, it turns out that most cities either do not plan to include stories in their implementation, opting instead for a custom homepage, or they prefer to disable the comment feature altogether. This decision also impacts other functionalities, such as analytics. Since the analytics were designed to provide insights based on user-generated stories, this feature becomes less applicable for most cities that do not allow public story submissions.

Finally, the requirements that are in the ‘Won’t Have’ category are requirements that will not be implemented. The main reason is that they were just suggestions from some partners, however, they are too complicated in terms of technical implementation, and there is lack of resources to implement them (automatic subtitles for video/audio files, automatic translation of the stories’ content). Additionally, some of them don’t align well with the core concept of the tool (forum).

Table 7: Final requirements along with their priorities

ID	Requirement	Priority
1	Users	
1.1	Registration to the platform	Must
1.2	Provide proof that they live in the city	Could
1.3	Provide information such as age, gender etc	Could
1.4	Registration with social login	Should
1.5	Different roles and access for citizens and cities	Must
1.6	Like stories	Should
1.7	Report stories	Should

1.8	Report comments	Should
1.9	Create tags	Should
1.10	Delete their stories	Must
1.11	Limit on number of comments under a story	Could
1.12	Limit on number of comments in a given timeframe	Could
1.13	Follow a story	Won't
2	Stories	
2.1	Template for creating new stories	Must
2.2	Story creation only for authenticated users	Must
2.3	Story text length limit	Should
2.4	Stories contain text	Must
2.5	Stories contain image	Must
2.6	Stories contain video	Should
2.7	Stories contain audio	Could
2.8	Stories contain combinations of formats like text over image	Must
2.9	Image gallery for stories	Should
2.10	Text prompts for stories	Should
2.11	Stories must have geographic information	Must
2.12	Comments	Could
2.13	Comment length limit	Should
2.14	Share to social media	Should
2.15	Stories must be displayed on a map	Must
2.16	Stories must be displayed on a timeline	Must
2.17	Stories have tags	Should
2.18	Predefined list with tags	Should

2.19	Filtered search of stories	Should
2.20	Limit on story pages	Should
2.21	Scrollytelling format	Must
2.22	Creator username should not be visible in the story	Should
2.23	Automatic creation of subtitles for the audio/video files that stories may have	Won't
2.24	Cities should approve each story before publishing it	Could
2.25	Cities should be able to disable comments	Must
2.26	Automatic translation of the stories content	Won't
3	Threads	
3.1	Cities can create Threads	Must
3.2	Thumbnail for the preview	Should
3.3	Threads should have tags	Should
3.4	Limit of stories under a thread	Could
3.5	Connection of threads with resources	Should
4	Resources	
4.1	Cities can create resources	Should
4.2	Different resources categories	Could
5	Home page	
5.1	Home page with scrollytelling format	Must
5.2	Template for creating and editing the home page	Could
6	General	
6.1	It should be inclusive	Should
6.2	Customised settings per city (disable/enable features)	Must
6.3	Available in the languages of the different cities (not the user-generated content)	Must
6.4	See stories from other cities	Could

6.5	Mobile friendly	Should
6.6	Analytics about the stories	Could
6.7	The tool should be available for a city	Must
6.8	The tool should be available for a neighbourhood	Could
6.9	The content must be available without registration	Must
6.10	Forum	Won't
6.11	Different basemaps for the map	Could
6.12	Cities can add extra layers on the map	Could
6.13	Story pins on map open the story preview when clicked	Should

3.2 [Technical Implementation](#)

3.2.1 [Mock-ups](#)

After the group interviews concluded at the beginning of M17, a comprehensive list of user requirements was compiled. With these user requirements approved by the cities that participated in the first round of co-design, the design of the mock-ups began. During M17, the focus was on creating the mock-ups that would be showcased in the Rotterdam workshop on June 3rd, 2024. The primary objective was to create as many pages of the tool as possible, ensuring that they meet the user requirements while also being user friendly and visually appealing. The tool used for this purpose was Figma, an application for designing UIs, which allows to efficiently translate the user requirements into a real UI. For the visual design of the UI, inspiration was mainly drawn from the UP2030 project website, incorporating the project's colour scheme to maintain consistency and alignment with the project identity. Keeping the same visual identity is all the more important considering that the platform will be linked to the project website.

By the end of the month, most of the key components of the tool were successfully designed, including the Stories, Threads and Resources pages, as well as the full-screen story page and the page for creating a new story. All these designs are presented in the following paragraphs along with images from the actual mock-ups.

Figure 2: Mock-up of the Stories page

Figure 2 displays the stories page. Like most of the tool's pages, it includes a navigation bar at the top. On the left of the bar, next to the logo, there is the name of the currently selected city and neighbourhood. In the centre, there are navigation links to the Stories, Threads, and Resources pages. On the right, there is a 'Create' button for creating a new story, a language selection button, a notifications button (indicating any notifications), and the user button that opens a menu with additional options.

The Stories page consists of the timeline on the left and the map on the right. On the right side of the timeline header, there is a 'Filters' button, which opens options to filter the stories displayed on both the timeline and the map. The filters could be the creation date, the tags, number of likes etc. The timeline shows previews of the stories. Each component on the top displays some information about the story such as the name of the story creator, the date of creation, and if applicable, the relevant neighbourhood and the associated thread. The three-dot button on the top-right corner opens a menu with options such as reporting the story. Then, there is the story's text and images, followed by the tags associated with the story. The number of likes and comments is displayed next, and on the bottom, there are three buttons: the 'Like' button for liking the story, the 'Comment' button (which opens a window to view and add comments), and the 'Share' button for sharing the story on social media. The map on the right has pins that represent the stories on the timeline, positioned according to their geographic information.

When a story in the timeline is clicked, it opens in full screen, as shown in Figure 3. Each story consists of multiple pages, each with a different format. For the mock-up, a story was created where each page features an image with overlay text. In full-screen, the image covers the entire screen, and the text is positioned inside a user-selected position. The information of the story like the name of the creator are displayed on the top, the buttons for the different actions such as liking the story are on the bottom and

on the top-right corner of the page there is the close button to return to the Stories page and the three-dot button with the same functionality as in the story preview.

Figure 3: Full-screen story page

When clicking the Create button in the navigation bar, a new page opens for creating a new story (Figure 4). The first step involves creating the story's content. Users can add pages by clicking the 'Add Part' button, with each added element representing a page. The type of content that is image, video, or audio can be selected from the respective dropdown menu. For Image content, users must upload an image or choose one from the city-provided gallery and add overlay text. The text's position is selected from a list with pre-defined options. In the next step, users can attach tags, choose a thread, and select the neighbourhood the story belongs to. Then, they can pinpoint the story's location on a map. The final step before publishing is a preview of the story.

Figure 4: The four steps of creating a new story

The Threads page, as shown in Figure 5, consists of the list with the thread previews on the left and a map displaying their locations on the right. The Filters button at the header of the list offers various options to filter the threads (such as tags, number of stories, creation date, etc.), and under the header there is a search field that allows users to find specific threads. Each thread preview includes the thread's name (e.g., t/Dioikitirio Square), the associated neighbourhood (e.g., Dioikitirio), a brief description of the topic of the thread, the number of stories it contains, and the associated tags. When a thread preview is clicked, the thread page opens (Figure 6), displaying the full description of the thread and the individual stories submitted to it. The map on the right shows pins marking the locations of these stories.

Figure 5: Threads page

Figure 6: Individual thread page

Figure 7: Resources page

Finally, the last mock-up that was designed during this period was the Resources page (Figure 7). This page provides filtering options in the top-right corner of the page (Filters button) and a search field for finding specific resources. Resources are organised by the city into different sections based on their topic or purpose, such as tutorials or educational material. Each section has a ‘See All’ button, which opens a page displaying all resources within that category.

3.2.2 1st coded version of the tool

Following the workshop in Rotterdam on June 3rd, 2024 (M18), and the update of user requirements based on the feedback received, the development of the web application for the tool began. The development started in early M18 and is still ongoing. The following sections describe the tool’s UI, and the technologies used in its development.

UI

When a user enters the [NSM Platform](#), they first see the Stories page (Figure 8). No authentication is required to just browse the content. While the application’s interface is consistent across all cities, each city has its own content, such as different stories, threads, resources, etc. Most of the pages in the application feature a navigation bar at the top, with the main content area below that changing based on the selected page.

Figure 8: Stories page

The navigation bar (Figure 9) contains the following elements, from left to right:

- The UP2030 logo
- The name of the selected city: clicking on it open a dialog component where user can select another city from the available ones. When the city changes the content of the application reloads to show the data specific to this city.
- Navigation link to the Stories page.
- Create button: this button leads to the page for creating a new story.
- Sign in button: For signing into the application. If a user is already signed in, this button is replaced by the user avatar. Clicking the avatar opens a menu with the following options:
 - Dashboard: Opens the Dashboard page (it is still under development and so it will not be presented in this deliverable)
 - Logout: Logs the user out

Figure 9: Navigation bar

The Stories page is composed of the stories' timeline on the left and the map on the right. The timeline presents a list of story previews, displayed in descending order based on their creation date. The map is focused on the selected city, with the pins indicating the geographic locations of the stories according to their geo-information.

Story previews in the timeline are displayed as shown in Figure 8. At the top, there is the username of the story's creator, followed by the creation date. Below this, the story's text is displayed, comprising the text content from the various pages of the story. If the text exceeds three lines, it is truncated, and a 'Show

more' button is added at the end. Clicking this button reveals the full text. The images associated with the story are displayed below the text; if there are multiple images, they appear in an image carousel that allows users to navigate through them. Beneath the images, the story's tags are displayed. At the bottom of the story component, there is a like button, which requires the user to be signed in to be able to like the story.

Figure 10: Story in full-screen presentation

When a user clicks on a story preview in the timeline, the story opens in full screen on a new page (Figure 10), presented in a scrollytelling format. This means that as the user scrolls down, the story unfolds in a dynamic way. Each page of the story is composed of an image and accompanying text. The image fills the entire background, taking up the full screen, while the text is displayed inside a box centred on the image. As the user scrolls down the page, the story unfolds: when the text of the next story part comes into view, the current image gradually fades out, and the next image fades in, creating a seamless transition between the story pages. The final part of each story features a map with a pin marking the story's geographic location. At the bottom centre of this section, there's a button with an arrow icon; clicking it takes the user to the next story. Moreover, when clicking on the story some additional elements appear on the screen. A close button on the top-right corner of the page to return to the Stories page, the username and the creation date in an element at the top-centre of the page, and the like button at the bottom.

To sign in to the app, the user needs to click on the 'Sign In' button located in the navigation bar, which will direct them to the sign-in page. In this page the user can enter the username and password in the respective fields and then click the 'Sign In' button. If they don't have an account, they can click on the 'Sign Up' link below the 'Sign In' button. Additionally, there is the 'Return Home' button which allows users to go back to the application's start page. On the sign-up page, users are asked to provide an email address, username, password, select a city, and choose a role (citizen or organisation). If a user already has an account but is on the sign-up page, they can easily navigate back to the sign-in page by clicking the 'Sign In' link beneath the 'Sign Up' button. To return to the app, they can click the 'Return Home' button.

When a user is logged in and clicks the Create button in the navigation bar, a new page opens with the steps for creating a new story. At the top of this page, there is a navigation element that displays the

number and title of each step, with the current step highlighted. There are four steps in the story creation process: Content, Information, Location, and Preview. On the bottom-right side of the page, there are Next and Back buttons for navigating through the different steps.

The screenshot shows a web application interface for creating a new story. At the top, there is a header with the 'UP2030' logo, the text 'Thessaloniki', a 'Stories' icon, a '+ Create' button, and a user profile icon. Below the header, the main area is titled 'Create new story'. A progress bar at the top of this section shows four steps: 1. Content (highlighted in green), 2. Information, 3. Location, and 4. Preview. Underneath the progress bar, the text 'Story part 1' is displayed. The main content area contains a form for adding a story part. It starts with a 'Type of content' dropdown menu set to 'Image'. Below this, there are two input fields: 'Image *' and 'Text *'. The 'Image *' field has an 'Upload file' button and a 'Gallery' link. The 'Text *' field is a large text area. Below these fields is a 'Text position' dropdown menu set to 'Center-center'. At the bottom left of the form is a '+ Add part' button. At the bottom right of the form are 'Back' and 'Next' buttons.

Figure 11: Page of the first step of creating a new story

In the Content step (Figure 11), the user defines the content of the new story, which currently consists of an image and text for each story page. Each story page element offers some options. At the top, the user can select the type of media for the respective part, with 'image' being the only available option right now. The user can then upload an image and add text using the respective inputs. Below the last story page element, there is an 'Add Part' button. Clicking this button adds a new story page element. There is currently a limit of three pages per story. When multiple story pages exist, each element includes an 'X' button in the top-right corner that can be used to delete it.

Clicking the 'Next' button, the user goes to the next step, 'Information,' where they can select the tags for the story. The following step, 'Location,' allows the user to set the story's position on the map. The final step, 'Preview,' displays a preview of the story. In this last step, the 'Next' button is replaced by a 'Publish' button, which, when clicked, creates and publishes the new story.

Technologies

For the development of the web application, the JavaScript library [React](#) is used due to its component-based architecture, which facilitates modular and scalable development. Along with React, [Material UI](#) is used, a popular library that provides a wide range of ready-to-use UI components. Material UI is useful for faster development and for providing components that adhere the modern design principles. To manage the application's state more efficiently, especially as it scales, [Redux](#) is used. Redux centralises the application's state, making it easier to manage complex state logic, reduce redundancy, and improve the predictability of state transitions within React.

The interactive maps in the application are powered by [Mapbox](#), a robust mapping platform that allows to integrate customisable, high-performance maps for the web.

Data storage and content management are handled using [Strapi](#), a powerful, open-source Node.js headless CMS. Strapi uses its built-in PostgreSQL database for data storage. In addition, Strapi allows to create a REST API, which is used to fetch and manage data on the front end, ensuring smooth and efficient interaction between the application's backend and frontend.

4 Timeline for future activities

The first iteration of co-design developed the methodology for NSM, aligned the concept of the platform with the vision of the different pilots, and developed a first version of the platform based on the first list of user requirements obtained from the different co-design activities described above (see Section 3). The second iteration of co-design will include more co-design activities to ensure that all pilot cities have an NSM by the end of the project (M36), populated with stories from either citizens, cities, or both (D6.7). From M19 to M36, the VUB and CERTH will conduct the following activities:

1. Continue having the preparatory meetings that started in M19 to brainstorm together with the cities what their prototype of NSM is, and how to achieve it together by M26. Meetings have already been held with 9 out of the 10 cities.
2. Train the cities that chose Option 1 and/or 2 and citizens to use the tool so they can create their digital stories by M26.
3. For the cities that chose Option 3, co-creation sessions will be organised to develop their first version of the NSM webpage.
4. Populate each NSM with the content co-created with the cities and/or citizens and simultaneously gather additional usability requirements to see how users perceive the different functionalities of the tool and the difficulty or ease of use.
5. Refine the NSM prototype for each city based on the feedback received until M30.
6. Public launch of the platform in M30.
7. Gather feedback on the public version of the platform from a wider audience to refine it and implement new user requirements and remaining features.

Please bear in mind that this is a preliminary timeline, and it is subject to change depending on different project related and pilot specific developments.

Table 8: Preliminary Timeline of Future Activities

Activity	Month																	
	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
1	█	█	█	█														
2				█	█													
3				█	█	█	█	█										
4				█	█	█	█	★										
5								█	█	█	█							
6													X					

5 Conclusion

The development and implementation of the NSM platform within the UP2030 project represent a significant step forward in enhancing citizen engagement and participation in urban climate action. By integrating digital storytelling with geospatial mapping, NSM offers a novel way for cities to communicate climate-related challenges and for citizens to share their lived experiences and aspirations regarding climate neutrality.

Throughout the first round of co-design, the collaboration between the VUB, CERTH, and the pilot cities has been instrumental in shaping the initial version of the NSM platform. This co-creative process has ensured that the platform is not only technically sound but also responsive to the unique needs and priorities of each city determined through various co-design activities (see Section 3). The feedback gathered from cities during workshops, interviews, and surveys has been critical in refining the user requirements and the overall structure of the tool, laying a strong foundation for the second iteration of co-design, during which the platform will be populated with digital stories.

As the project progresses, the focus will shift towards further refinement of the platform based on the additional feedback from the pilot cities and the expansion of its functionalities to better serve the diverse needs of urban stakeholders. The goal is to have a fully operational NSM for each pilot city (D6.7) by the end of the project (M36), with each map populated with meaningful digital stories that reflect the local context and engage the community in the journey towards climate neutrality. The continuation of the co-design process, coupled with the public launch of the platform, will be crucial in realising the full potential of NSM. As cities begin to use the platform to share and explore climate stories, more requirements related to the usability of the platform will arise, and the platform will be fine-tuned accordingly.

In conclusion, the NSM platform is not just a tool for communication but a catalyst for change, empowering citizens and cities to collaborate in addressing the pressing challenges of climate change. The work done so far sets a promising trajectory for the remaining phases of the project, with the anticipation that NSM will play a key role in shaping the climate-resilient cities of the future.

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Annex

Annex 1: Survey Results

City you are representing	Sum of To what extent do you believe that public awareness and engagement activities are useful and important in helping cities achieve climate neutrality goals in your city?
Belfast	5
Budapest	5
Granollers	4
Istanbul	4
Lisbon	5
Milan	4
Münster	4
Rotterdam	5
Thessaloniki	5
Zagreb	5

City you are representing	Does your city communicate with citizens about your work on achieving your climate neutrality goals?
<input type="checkbox"/> Belfast	Yes
Belfast Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Budapest	Yes
Budapest Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Granollers	Yes
Granollers Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Istanbul	Yes
Istanbul Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Lisbon	Yes
Lisbon Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Milan	Yes
Milan Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Münster	Yes
Münster Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Rotterdam	Yes
Rotterdam Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Thessaloniki	Yes
Thessaloniki Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Zagreb	Yes
Zagreb Total	

City you are representing	If yes, what types of communication channels do you use to communicate and engage with citizens about your work on your city's climate neutrality goals?
<input type="checkbox"/> Belfast	Online
Belfast Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Budapest	Online
Budapest Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Granollers	Combination of online and offline channels
Granollers Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Istanbul	Combination of online and offline channels
Istanbul Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Lisbon	Combination of online and offline channels
Lisbon Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Milan	Combination of online and offline channels
Milan Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Münster	Combination of online and offline channels
Münster Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Rotterdam	Combination of online and offline channels
Rotterdam Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Thessaloniki	Offline
Thessaloniki Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Zagreb	Combination of online and offline channels
Zagreb Total	

City you are representing	Is your city interested in trying new ways of communicating with citizens, like using digital storytelling, to engage a wider audience and advance your climate neutrality goals?
<input type="checkbox"/> Belfast	Maybe
Belfast Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Budapest	Yes
Budapest Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Granollers	Yes
Granollers Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Istanbul	Maybe
Istanbul Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Lisbon	Maybe
Lisbon Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Milan	Yes
Milan Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Münster	No
Münster Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Rotterdam	Maybe
Rotterdam Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Thessaloniki	Yes
Thessaloniki Total	
<input type="checkbox"/> Zagreb	Maybe
Zagreb Total	

City you are representing | **What profile of citizen is most engaged in climate change efforts and awareness (i.e., age range, gender, socio-economic background, employment status, profession, local businesses, schools, urban planners etc.) in your city?**

- Belfast** Young people, schools, universities, place makers
- Belfast Total**
- Budapest** according to our surveys: 14-50, women, middle and upper income, with higher education
- Budapest Total**
- Granollers** Youth and middle age population with diverse socio-economic origins. Generally active population, education communities, administration and private sector technicians and other people with high and medium cultural level
- Granollers Total**
- Istanbul** Youngs, high educated
- Istanbul Total**
- Lisbon** children/families, students, researchers, general public, NGOs, CML workers, media, men and women
- Lisbon Total**
- Milan** Students in schools thanks to environmental education activities
- Milan Total**
- Münster** That is difficult to say, we have wide range of different engagement tools and forms . Maybe the citizen of the middle class (educational background and middle income
- Münster Total**
- Rotterdam** (blank)
- Rotterdam Total**
- Thessaloniki** its hard to categorize, we have seen engaged citizens with different background and age
- Thessaloniki Total**
- Zagreb** Schools, Urban Planners, Local Business
- Zagreb Total**

City you are representing | **What profile of citizen is not as invested and that you would hope to engage in climate change efforts and awareness (i.e., age range, gender, socio-economic background, employment status, profession, local businesses, schools, urban planners etc.) in your city?**

- Belfast** Older generations, perhaps those in areas of deprivation that are facing multiple socio-economic challenges and struggle to prioritise climate issues
- Belfast Total**
- Budapest** elderly, less educated, men
- Budapest Total**
- Granollers** It is generally difficult for us to reach new citizens, with cultural diversity and of various ages
- Granollers Total**
- Istanbul** vulnerable people
- Istanbul Total**
- Lisbon** general public, students
- Lisbon Total**
- Milan** Adults in general, with differences depending on the socio-economic background.
- Milan Total**
- Münster** Statistically, it is citizens with higher incomes and/or assets who have the largest carbon footprint. This makes them an important target group.
- Münster Total**
- Rotterdam** (blank)
- Rotterdam Total**
- Thessaloniki** all citizens of all ages and gender
- Thessaloniki Total**
- Zagreb** elderly population, vulnerable groups, business corporations
- Zagreb Total**

City you are representing | **Do you see the Neutrality Story Maps tool aligning with some of your planned activities or citizen engagement strategies in your city?**

- Belfast** Yes
- Belfast Total**
- Budapest** Yes
- Budapest Total**
- Granollers** Yes
- Granollers Total**
- Istanbul** Yes
- Istanbul Total**
- Lisbon** Yes
- Lisbon Total**
- Milan** Yes
- Milan Total**
- Münster** No
- Münster Total**
- Rotterdam** Yes
- Rotterdam Total**
- Thessaloniki** Yes
- Thessaloniki Total**
- Zagreb** Yes
- Zagreb Total**

City you are representing	What problems have you faced or expect to face when communicating and engaging citizens in your city's climate neutrality initiatives?
Belfast Total	Competing priorities such as cost of living crisis, lack of resource and opportunities to support transformation, difficult for people to contextualise how climate neutrality will involve/affect them, making the case for behaviour change at a micro level compared to the responsibility of larger corporations
Budapest Total	reach out to mainstream media, budget sensitive measures
Granollers Total	Lack of understanding of concepts as climate neutrality, resilience, social inclusion, etc. also lack of knowledge on climate effects and the potential benefits of mitigation and adaptation measures to guarantee their quality of life
Istanbul Total	financial priorities
Lisbon Total	alignment between communication plans of different promoters, budget
Milan Total	Difficulties in the use of municipal communication channels (mainly institutional social networks) as they are managed by other internal departments.
Münster Total	A lot of public relations work is necessary. Many processes are too singular. There is a high level of awareness among the people, but it is difficult to take action.
Rotterdam Total	(blank)
Thessaloniki Total	lack of trust that the city will find the resources to meet the goals
Zagreb Total	lack of knowledge and level of awareness; lack of funding; the different level of development of individual parts of the city generates different communal needs, which results in different acceptance or non-acceptance of certain advanced projects; challenges of including less educated groups in the
City you are representing	Would you be interested in joining the first or second round of co-design activities of the tool?
Belfast Total	2nd round: interviews, surveys, and focus groups from October 2024 onwards to refine and finalize the tool by the end of the project (exact dates to be determined)
Budapest Total	I am interested in participating in both rounds
Granollers Total	2nd round: interviews, surveys, and focus groups from October 2024 onwards to refine and finalize the tool by the end of the project (exact dates to be determined)
Istanbul Total	2nd round: interviews, surveys, and focus groups from October 2024 onwards to refine and finalize the tool by the end of the project (exact dates to be determined)
Lisbon Total	2nd round: interviews, surveys, and focus groups from October 2024 onwards to refine and finalize the tool by the end of the project (exact dates to be determined)
Milan Total	I am interested in participating in both rounds
Münster Total	1st round: co-design online workshop in March-April 2024 and workshop to get feedback on the mockups in May-June 2024
Rotterdam Total	2nd round: interviews, surveys, and focus groups from October 2024 onwards to refine and finalize the tool by the end of the project (exact dates to be determined)
Thessaloniki Total	I am interested in participating in both rounds
Zagreb Total	1st round: co-design online workshop in March-April 2024 and workshop to get feedback on the mockups in May-June 2024

Annex 2: Interview Questionnaire

1. Icebreaker: Could you briefly introduce yourself and describe your current position at the municipality? How long have you been working in that position? Level of seniority?
2. Could you share your experience with citizen engagement and participatory initiatives at the municipality?
 - a. What was the purpose for the citizen engagement and/or participatory initiatives?
 - b. What worked well? What worked less well?
 - c. Mention answers of follow-up questionnaire from the pilot city: 1. What profiles are the usual suspects? 2. What profiles would you like to engage? 3. Challenges when engaging citizens.
 - d. On what basis was this engagement strategy created? By whom?
3. What other (digital) citizen engagement tools have you used?
 - a. Do you have experience with other digital storytelling tools?
4. How do you see the tool aligning with some of your planned activities or engagement strategy?
 - a. What goals might you have in mind that this tool could help you accomplish? (Mention the initiatives planned by each city (e.g. Climate Training, Climate Proofing for Münster)
5. What's the level of engagement that you are aiming for?
 - a. Top-down: City as a storyteller and citizens as recipients.
 - b. Bottom-up: Citizens as storytellers and city as recipient (more like a consultancy approach)

- c. Collaborative: Citizens upload stories, city compiles an article out of these stories to share on the platform, so citizens interact with the stories etc. Or for instance the city uploads a new mobility scheme on a map that citizens can provide input on through image overlay on map or stories etc.

- d. Why this approach?

1) *Manipulation, therapy? (non-participation) 2) Informing, consultation, placation? (degrees of tokenism)*

3) *Partnership, delegated power, citizen control? (degrees of citizen power) (Arnstein, 1969)*

- 6. Who would you expect to be the users of this tool in your city?

- a. Who is the storyteller (users who actively engage by creating their own stories) and who is the audience?

- b. Citizens: Which profiles? For what purpose?

- c. Policymakers: Which profiles? Will there be personnel at your city in charge of monitoring the platform? Uploading (educational) material? Providing trainings? How will communication be handled?

- d. Different stakeholders (Local businesses, urban planners etc.): Which profiles? For what purpose?

- 7. Requirements:

- a. Storytelling:

- i. Characteristics of a story:

- 1. Format: text, video, audio, image, or combination of these formats (more options will be explored like text over image or image overlay on map). Would you like to have an interactive template?

- 2. Categories: As the creator of the story, would you like to be able to add some predefined categories/tags to the story (e.g. recycling, green, transportation etc.)?

- 3. How do you expect the stories to be presented?

- a. Like social media posts where there is an image(s)/video and text under/over that image(s)?

- b. Like a website article with text, images, video?

- c. On a timeline and on the map? (Filtered view: dates, geographic location, tags, threads etc.)

- d. Do you expect the stories to be short or be like blog articles?

- 4. Thread: Do you want the story to be an independent one or under a thread predefined by the city/citizens or both?

- 5. Geographic location (each story should have geoinformation to be able to be displayed on a map): How would you want to include the geo-information? By directly putting a pin and introducing the story? Would you like the option to make the tool available in certain neighbourhoods or the whole city depending on your planned initiatives?

- 6. Do you believe citizens in your city should have access to stories from other cities? How significant do you think this access is? (The platform will be available in different languages but not the content of the platform.)

- 7. Would you like users to react to the stories? If so, how?

- a. Like button, comments, share button to social media platforms.
- b. Community monitoring (ability to, report comments or stories).
- c. What insights would you hope to get from Neutrality Story Maps?
 - i. What information would you like to be able to gather from the tool? In what form?
 - ii. What kind of analytics do you expect the tool to provide to you? (Key word analysis, engagement trends, statistics (stories per day, per tag, location etc.))
8. What aspect of the tool will be most valuable to you? Least valuable?
9. What would prevent you from using this tool?
10. What kind of support would you need to start using this tool?
11. How long will you be using the tool for? Time of overall use of the platform (No use after the project ends or continue to introduce stories after the project ends).

Annex 3: Post-Workshop Survey Report

1

First Name	Last Name	City you are representing	Current position
Zoltán	Erdős	Budapest	Active and Micromobility Officer
Maria	Telhado	Lisbon (Portugal)	Director
Niamh	Mulrìne	Belfast	UP2030 Lead
Caroline	König	Münster	Deputy management
Elvin	ÖKSÜZ BAYAZIT	İstanbul	Environmental Engineer
Dimitra	Zouni	Thessaloniki	Project Officer
Judit	Tarradellas Font	Granollers	Environmental technician
Kinga	Feenstra	Rotterdam	Policy advisor
Sergej	Lugovic	Zagreb	CEO
Eleonora	Esposito	Milano	Project Manager

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

10 Responses

Budapest

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

No. They can create stories and have access to all the content of the platform without registration.

Lisbon (Portugal)

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

No. They can create stories and have access to all the content of the platform without registration.

Belfast

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

Yes, but only if they want to create stories. Not necessary if they only want to browse the website and watch stories and other content.

Münster

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

Yes, but only if they want to create stories. Not necessary if they only want to browse the website and watch stories and other content.

Istanbul

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

Yes.

Thessaloniki

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

No. They can create stories and have access to all the content of the platform without registration.

Granollers

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

Yes, but only if they want to create stories. Not necessary if they only want to browse the website and watch stories and other content.

Rotterdam

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

Yes, but only if they want to create stories. Not necessary if they only want to browse the website and watch stories and other content.

Zagreb

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

Yes, but only if they want to create stories. Not necessary if they only want to browse the website and watch stories and other content.

Milano

Do you want users to sign up/register in order to use Neutrality Story Maps platform?

No. They can create stories and have access to all the content of the platform without registration.

Sign up - If yes, what information do you want them to provide in order to be able to sign up/register? (The information collected when signing up will allow you to gather statistics about the users, engagement trends, and other analytics. However, you will be responsible for checking the documents that the new users provide as proof of residence in the neighbourhood/city.) -

6 Responses

Belfast

If yes, what information do you want them to provide in order to be able to sign up/register?

(The information collected when signing up will allow you to gather statistics about the users, engagement trends, and other analytics. However, you will be responsible for checking the documents that the new users provide as proof of residence in the neighbourhood/city.) - Selected Choice

Full Name, Age, Gender

Münster

If yes, what information do you want them to provide in order to be able to sign up/register?

(The information collected when signing up will allow you to gather statistics about the users, engagement trends, and other analytics. However, you will be responsible for checking the documents that the new users provide as proof of residence in the neighbourhood/city.) - Selected Choice

Full Name, Age

Istanbul

If yes, what information do you want them to provide in order to be able to sign up/register?

(The information collected when signing up will allow you to gather statistics about the users, engagement trends, and other analytics. However, you will be responsible for checking the documents that the new users provide as proof of residence in the neighbourhood/city.) - Selected Choice

Full Name, Age, Proof they reside in that neighbourhood/city, Ethnicity, Gender

Granollers

If yes, what information do you want them to provide in order to be able to sign up/register?

(The information collected when signing up will allow you to gather statistics about the users, engagement trends, and other analytics. However, you will be responsible for checking the documents that the new users provide as proof of residence in the neighbourhood/city.) - Selected Choice

Full Name, Other

Rotterdam

If yes, what information do you want them to provide in order to be able to sign up/register?

(The information collected when signing up will allow you to gather statistics about the users, engagement trends, and other analytics. However, you will be responsible for checking the documents that the new users provide as proof of residence in the neighbourhood/city.) - Selected Choice

Full Name, Proof they reside in that neighbourhood/city

Zagreb

If yes, what information do you want them to provide in order to be able to sign up/register?

(The information collected when signing up will allow you to gather statistics about the users, engagement trends, and other analytics. However, you will be responsible for checking the documents that the new users provide as proof of residence in the neighbourhood/city.) - Selected Choice

Full Name, Proof they reside in that neighbourhood/city

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

Budapest

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

3

Lisbon (Portugal)

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

7

Belfast

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

4

Münster

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

?

Istanbul

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

6

Thessaloniki

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

6

Granollers

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

For Granollers would be useful the representation of initial page with map, 3 pages with pillars, final page (1 or 2 pages) with render and street sections of proposals

Rotterdam

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

6

Zagreb

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

up to 10

Milano

Maximum number of pages if the city is the storyteller:

4

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

Budapest

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

2

Belfast

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

4

Münster

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

?

Istanbul

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

3

Thessaloniki

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

3-4

Rotterdam

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

2

Zagreb

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

max 5

Milano

Maximum number of pages if an individual user/citizen is the storyteller:

n.a

Map - How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map? The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

10 Responses

Budapest

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Avatars that symbolise personas from a gallery that the user could choose from. The personas will be co-created with the cities. (A persona is a fictional character that represents a type of user or a voice of a storyteller. A persona is created based on research or imagination, and is used to understand the needs, behaviours, goals, or experiences of a target audience or a storytelling purpose.)

Lisbon (Portugal)

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Belfast

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Münster

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Istanbul

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Thessaloniki

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Granollers

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Avatars that symbolise personas from a gallery that the user could choose from. The personas will be co-created with the cities. (A persona is a fictional character that represents a type of user or a voice of a storyteller. A persona is created based on research or imagination, and is used to understand the needs, behaviours, goals, or experiences of a target audience or a storytelling purpose.)

Rotterdam

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Zagreb

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Milano

How would you like the pins of stories to be presented on the map?

The pins will be interactive and when you press them, you will be able to see the name of the user and a short preview of the story.

Simple map pins.

Username - Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories? In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

10 Responses

Budapest

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

Yes.

Lisbon (Portugal)

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

No.

Belfast

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

No.

Münster

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

Yes.

Istanbul

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

No.

Thessaloniki

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

Yes.

Granollers

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

No.

Rotterdam

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

No.

Zagreb

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

Yes.

Milano

Should the username of the storyteller be visible in the timeline of stories?

In the example above it is "Nick Pantelidis" shown on the top left of the timeline.

No.

Profile photo - Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

10 Responses

Budapest

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

Yes

Lisbon (Portugal)

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

No

Belfast

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

Yes

Münster

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

No

İstanbul

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

No

Thessaloniki

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

Yes

Granollers

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

Yes

Rotterdam

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

No

Zagreb

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

Yes

Milano

Should a thumbnail with the profile photo of the storyteller (either their real photo or an avatar) be shown next to their username on the timeline?

No

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard? (Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

10 Responses

Budapest

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis

Lisbon (Portugal)

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis, Other

Belfast

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis, Engagement trends, Sentiment analysis, Statistics about the users (age, gender, address, etc.)

Münster

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

No analytics needed

Istanbul

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis, Engagement trends, Sentiment analysis, Statistics about the users (age, gender, address, etc.)

Thessaloniki

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis, Engagement trends, Statistics about the users (age, gender, address, etc.)

Granollers

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis, Engagement trends

Rotterdam

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis, Engagement trends, Sentiment analysis, Other

Zagreb

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

Key word(s) analysis, Engagement trends, Sentiment analysis, Statistics about the users (age, gender, address, etc.), Other

Milano

Which of these analytics do you want in your city dashboard?

(Please bear in mind that if users did not enter this information when signing up to use Neutrality Story Maps, gathering statistics about them such as their age, gender, and address will not be possible.) - Selected Choice

No analytics needed

QID13_5_TEXT - Other - Text

3 Responses

Lisbon (Portugal)

Other - Text

map

Rotterdam

Other - Text

Export statistics function

Zagreb

Other - Text

log analysis, google analytics, hub spot alike, CRM interactions with citizens story teller, dashboard

Annex 4: Consent Forms

Dear Madam/Sir,

You have been invited to participate in a group interview under the framework of the European project Urban Planning and design ready for 2030 (UP2030). UP2030 aims to guide cities through the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality ambitions. It will do so by enabling a quantum leap from a 'business as usual', project-by-project decarbonisation approach to a vision-driven, strategy-based approach that is anchored on sound projects and renewed policy development.

Ince, SVIT, Vrije universiteit Brussel (VUB) and CERTH's role in the project is to develop, test and validate citizen engagement state-of-the-art methods and digital tools, to support better decision-making on spatial solutions. With your participation you will make a substantial contribution in the development of the Neutrality Story Maps tool, which are map-based stories by citizens on the topic of climate change and climate transitions in the city. Neutrality Story Maps will generate informative and intimate accounts of citizens' lived experiences, insights, ideas, reflections, sensations, and thoughts that would otherwise remain unrevealed and unharnessed. Based on the concepts of digital storytelling, Neutrality Story Maps allow the sharing of experiences, issues, concerns, hopes and needs regarding climate and sustainability in the city through a narrative format.

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My participation will involve:

- A Group Interview.
- I am required to participate in the discussion by answering questions.
- The interview will take place online (Microsoft Teams).
- The interview is set to take +/- 1.5 hours.

Financed by the European Union, citizens and citizens' organisations, as members of the public, private and third sector. Programme policy financed by the European Union under the leadership of the European Commission and the European Parliament. The European Union is not responsible for the content of this document or for the use of the information contained therein. The project has received funding from the European Union under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 101019719.

1. Consent form

I have been provided with information about the task and my rights as a participant.

In relation to this task:

- I agree to take part in the group interview as a participant and complete all the exercises that aim to understand the end users' needs and objectives, which will be linked to the development of the mock-ups of the Neutrality Story Maps tool.
- I agree that my personal data which is gathered during and as the result of my participation in this task will be (i) collected and returned for the purpose of this project, and (ii) accessed and analyzed by the imec SMART VUB researchers for the purpose of developing the mock-ups of the Neutrality Story Maps tool.

I acknowledge that:

- My participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from participation at any time without explanation.
- My anonymity is guaranteed, and I will not be identified in publications or otherwise without my express written consent.
- I am aware of the legal ground on which the processing of my personal data is based, namely consent as per Art. 6 (1) (a) GDPR.¹
- I am aware that I might withdraw my consent for the processing of my personal data, however without affecting the lawfulness of the processing prior to the withdrawal of consent.
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 - ✓ The right to access.
 - ✓ The right to rectification.
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- I am aware that the controller and processor of my personal data provided in the context of this

UP2030 Consent Form

participation's VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels, company number 449.012.406. If you have questions or if you wish to exercise your rights, you can contact Milutin Djuraskovic (mailto:milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be) or the data protection officer of VUB (dpo@vub.be).

- I am aware that the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data are VUB.
- I have been informed of the procedure on how to exercise these rights with the controller, namely: sending an e-mail to milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be or the data protection officer of VUB (dpo@vub.be).
- I am aware of the purposes for which my data is gathered and processed in this project, namely: collecting user requirements based on which mock ups of the Neutrality Story Maps will be developed.
- My data will be protected and kept safe throughout this project and accessed and analysed by imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel researchers for the purpose of implementing this project. My data will be stored for the duration of the project and kept for 5 years after the final payment of Grant Agreement 101096405.

By signing this document, I agree to:

- participate in this group interview under the terms set out above and
- the processing of my personal data

My signature confirms that I accept and understand these conditions without reservation.

16.4.24 *Milutin*
Date & Place

[Handwritten Signature]
Signature

Contact

Milutin Djuraskovic; imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Researcher: milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be

Dear Madam/Sir,

You have been invited to participate in a group interview under the framework of the European project Urban Planning and design ready for 2030 (UP2030). UP2030 aims to guide cities through the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality ambitions. It will do so by enabling a quantum leap from a 'business as usual', project-by-project decarbonization approach to a vision-driven, strategy-based approach that is anchored on sound projects and renewed policy development.

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Financed by the European Union, through the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement. Content is the sole responsibility of CCRILI and does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. Neither the European Commission nor the project owners are responsible for any use of the information contained in this publication.

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participation is VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels, company number 119.012.406. If you have questions or if you wish to exercise your rights, you can contact Milutin Djuraskovic (mailto:mi.djuraskovic@vub.be) or the data protection officer of VUB (dpo@vub.be).

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- My data will be protected and kept safe throughout this project and accessed and analysed by Ineu-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel researchers for the purpose of implementing this project. My data will be stored for the duration of the project and kept for 5 years after the final payment of Grant Agreement 101096405.

By signing this document, I agree to:

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My signature confirms that I accept and understand these conditions without reservation.

Date & Place

16.09.24, Mander

Signature

Milutin Djuraskovic

Contact

Milutin Djuraskovic; Ineu-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Researcher; mi.djuraskovic@vub.be

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Date & Place

Signature

Contact

Milutin Djuraskovic; imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Researcher; Milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be

Αγαπητή/έ Κυρία/Κύριε,

Στα πλαίσια του Ευρωπαϊκού Προγράμματος Urban Planning and design ready for 2030 (UP2030), έχετε προσκληθεί να συμμετάσχετε σε μια ομαδική συνέντευξη. Το UP2030 έχει ως στόχο να καθοδηγήσει τις πόλεις, μέσα από τις κοινωνικο-τεχνικές μεταβάσεις που απαιτούνται, για να ανταποκριθούν στις φιλοδοξίες τους για την κλιματική ουδετερότητα. Αυτό θα το πράξει κάνοντας ένα τεράστιο άλμα από τη συνήθη έργο-προς-έργο προσέγγιση απαλλαγής από τις ανθρακούχες εκπομπές, σε μια οραματική προσέγγιση βασισμένη σε στρατηγική που στηρίζεται σε υγιή έργα και ανανεωμένη πολιτική ανάπτυξης.

Ο ρόλος των [imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel \(VUB\)](#) και [CERTH](#) στο έργο είναι η ανάπτυξη, δοκιμή και επικύρωση μεθόδων τελευταίας τεχνολογίας και ψηφιακών εργαλείων για τη συμμετοχή των πολιτών, για την υποστήριξη της καλύτερης λήψης αποφάσεων για χωρικές λύσεις. Με τη συμμετοχή σας θα συμβάλετε ουσιαστικά στην ανάπτυξη του εργαλείου Neutrality Story Maps, το οποίο αναπαριστά ιστορίες πολιτών που απεικονίζονται σε χάρτες με θέμα την κλιματική αλλαγή και τις κλιματικές μεταβάσεις στην πόλη. Το εργαλείο Neutrality Story Maps θα δημιουργήσει ενημερωτικές και προσωπικές αναφορές πολιτών σχετικά με βιωμένες εμπειρίες, γνώσεις, ιδέες, στοχασμούς, αισθήσεις και σκέψεις, που διαφορετικά θα παρέμεναν άγνωστες και ανεκμετάλλετες. Βασισμένο στις έννοιες της ψηφιακής αφήγησης, το εργαλείο Neutrality Story Maps επιτρέπει την ανταλλαγή εμπειριών, ζητημάτων, ανησυχιών, ελπίδων και αναγκών σχετικά με το κλίμα και τη βιωσιμότητα στην πόλη μέσω μιας μορφής αφήγησης.

Η συλλογή δεδομένων για την ανάπτυξη του εργαλείου θα γίνει σε δύο φάσεις: 1. Για να αναπτύξουμε την πρώτη έκδοση του εργαλείου θα σας ζητηθεί να συμμετάσχετε σε μια ομαδική συνέντευξη βάσει των οποίων θα αναπτυχθούν μακέτες του εργαλείου. Στη συνέχεια, τα σχόλια για τις μακέτες του εργαλείου θα συγκεντρωθούν σε μια ομάδα εστίασης (focus group) στην εκδήλωση Cities Knowledge Exchange στο Ρότερνταμ αυτόν τον Ιούνιο. Επομένως, η πρώτη έκδοση του εργαλείου θα αναπτυχθεί με βάση τα δεδομένα που συλλέχθηκαν κατά τις ομαδικές συνεντεύξεις και τα σχόλια που συγκεντρώθηκαν σχετικά με τις μακέτες. 2. Στη δεύτερη φάση του από κοινού σχεδιασμού, θα οργανωθεί άλλος ένας γύρος δραστηριοτήτων από κοινού σχεδιασμού, συμπεριλαμβανομένων συνεντεύξεων, ερευνών και πιθανώς εργαστηρίων για τη συλλογή των απαιτήσεων ενός μεγαλύτερου δείγματος ενδιαφερομένων, προκειμένου να τελειοποιηθεί και να οριστικοποιηθεί η τελευταία έκδοση του εργαλείου για όλες τις πιλοτικές πόλεις. Παρακαλούμε να λάβετε υπόψη ότι είστε ελεύθεροι να επιλέξετε σε πόσα βήματα θέλετε να συμμετάσχετε. Μπορείτε, για παράδειγμα, να συμμετάσχετε σε ένα βήμα ή σε όλα.

Η συμμετοχή μου θα περιλαμβάνει:

- Μια ομαδική συνέντευξη.
- Μου ζητείται να συμμετέχω στη συζήτηση απαντώντας σε ερωτήσεις.
- Η συνέντευξη θα γίνει διαδικτυακά (Microsoft Teams).
- Η συνέντευξη θα διαρκέσει +/- 1.5 ώρα.

1. Φόρμα συγκατάθεσης

Έχω ενημερωθεί σχετικά με τις υποχρεώσεις και τα δικαιώματά μου ως συμμετέχων/ουσα.

Σε σχέση με το αντικείμενο της έρευνας:

- Συμφωνώ να λάβω μέρος στην ομαδική συνέντευξη ως συμμετέχων/ουσα και να ολοκληρώσω όλες τις ασκήσεις που στοχεύουν στην κατανόηση των αναγκών και των στόχων των τελικών χρηστών, οι οποίοι θα συνδέονται με την ανάπτυξη των μακετών του εργαλείου Neutrality Story Maps.
- Συμφωνώ ότι τα προσωπικά μου δεδομένα που συλλέγονται κατά τη διάρκεια και ως αποτέλεσμα της συμμετοχής μου σε αυτήν την εργασία (i) θα συλλέγονται και θα διατηρούνται για τους σκοπούς αυτού του έργου και (ii) θα είναι προσβάσιμα και θα αναλύονται από τους ερευνητές του Imec-SMIT VUB με σκοπό την ανάπτυξη μακέτας του εργαλείου Neutrality Story Maps.

Αναγνωρίζω ότι:

- Η συμμετοχή μου είναι εθελοντική και είμαι ελεύθερος/η να αποχωρήσω κάθε στιγμή χωρίς εξήγηση.
- Η ανωνυμία μου είναι εγγυημένη και δε θα ταυτοποιηθώ σε δημοσιεύσεις ή αλλού χωρίς τη γραπτή συγκατάθεσή μου.
- Γνωρίζω τη νομική βάση στην οποία βασίζεται η επεξεργασία των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων, δηλαδή τη συγκατάθεση σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 6 (1) (a) GDPR.¹
- Γνωρίζω ότι ενδέχεται να αποσύρω τη συγκατάθεσή μου για την επεξεργασία των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων, χωρίς ωστόσο να επηρεάζεται η νομιμότητα της επεξεργασίας πριν από την ανάκληση της συγκατάθεσης.
- Γνωρίζω ότι έχω τα ακόλουθα δικαιώματα ως υποκείμενο των δεδομένων, τα οποία μπορώ να ασκήσω με τον υπεύθυνο επεξεργασίας:
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα στην πρόσβαση.
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα στη διόρθωση.
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα στη διαγραφή.
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα στον περιορισμό επεξεργασίας.
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα ενημέρωσης για τους παραλήπτες μετά από αίτημα διόρθωσης, διαγραφής ή περιορισμού της επεξεργασίας.
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα στη φορητότητα των δεδομένων.
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα αντίρρησης.
 - ✓ Το δικαίωμα να μην υπόκειμαι σε αυτοματοποιημένη ατομική λήψη αποφάσεων, συμπεριλαμβανομένης της κατάρτισης προφίλ.

✓ Να υποβάλω καταγγελία στην εθνική μου Αρχή Προστασίας Δεδομένων.

- Γνωρίζω ότι ο υπεύθυνος χειρισμού και επεξεργασίας των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων που παρέχονται στο πλαίσιο αυτής της συμμετοχής είναι το VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels, αριθμός εταιρείας 449.012.406. Εάν έχετε ερωτήσεις ή εάν επιθυμείτε να ασκήσετε τα δικαιώματά σας, μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε με τον Milutin Djuraskovic (milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be) ή τον υπεύθυνο προστασίας δεδομένων της VUB (dpo@vub.be).
- Γνωρίζω ότι οι παραλήπτες ή κατηγορίες παραληπτών των προσωπικών δεδομένων είναι το VUB.
- Έχω ενημερωθεί για τη διαδικασία σχετικά με τον τρόπο άσκησης αυτών των δικαιωμάτων με τον υπεύθυνο χειρισμού των δεδομένων, και συγκεκριμένα: αποστολή ενός e-mail στη διεύθυνση milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be ή στον υπεύθυνο προστασίας δεδομένων της VUB (dpo@vub.be).
- Γνωρίζω τους σκοπούς για τους οποίους συλλέγονται και υποβάλλονται σε επεξεργασία τα δεδομένα μου σε αυτό το έργο, και συγκεκριμένα: συλλογή απαιτήσεων χρήστη βάσει των οποίων θα αναπτυχθούν μακέτες του εργαλείου Neutrality Story Maps.
- Τα δεδομένα μου θα προστατεύονται και θα διατηρούνται ασφαλή καθ' όλη τη διάρκεια αυτού του έργου και θα είναι προσβάσιμα και θα αναλύονται από ερευνητές του imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel για τους σκοπούς της υλοποίησης αυτού του έργου. Τα δεδομένα μου θα αποθηκευτούν για τη διάρκεια του έργου και θα διατηρηθούν για 5 χρόνια μετά την τελική πληρωμή της Συμφωνίας Επιχορήγησης 101096405.

Υπογράφοντας το παρόν έγγραφο, συμφωνώ:

- να συμμετέχω στην ομαδική συνέντευξη υπό τους όρους που τέθηκαν παραπάνω και
- στην επεξεργασία των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων

Η υπογραφή μου επιβεβαιώνει πως αποδέχομαι και καταλαβαίνω αυτούς τους όρους χωρίς επιφύλαξη.

Ημερομηνία & Μέρος

19/04/2024

Υπογραφή

MILUTIN DJURASKOVIC

Επικοινωνία

Milutin Djuraskovic; imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Researcher; Milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be

Dear Madam/Sir,

You have been invited to participate in a group interview under the framework of the European project Urban Planning and design ready for 2030 (UP2030). UP2030 aims to guide cities through the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality ambitions. It will do so by enabling a quantum leap from a 'business as usual', project-by-project decarbonisation approach to a vision-driven, strategy-based approach that is anchored on sound projects and renewed policy development.

[Imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel \(VUB\)](#) and [CERTH](#)'s role in the project is to develop, test and validate citizen engagement state-of-the-art methods and digital tools, to support better decision-making on spatial solutions. With your participation you will make a substantial contribution to the development of the Neutrality Story Maps tool, which are map-based stories by citizens on the topic of climate change and climate transitions in the city. Neutrality Story Maps will generate informative and intimate accounts of citizens' lived experiences, insights, ideas, reflections, sensations, and thoughts that would otherwise remain unrevealed and unharnessed. Based on the concepts of digital storytelling, Neutrality Story Maps allow the sharing of experiences, issues, concerns, hopes and needs regarding climate and sustainability in the city through a narrative format.

User requirement collection for the development of the tool will happen in two phases: 1. To develop the first version of the tool you will be asked to participate in a group interview based on which mock-ups of the tool will be developed. Then feedback on the mock-ups of the tool will be gathered in a focus group in the Cities Knowledge Exchange event in Rotterdam this June. The first version of the tool will be therefore developed based on the data collected during the group interviews and the feedback gathered on the mock-ups. 2. In the second phase of co-design, another round of co-design activities including interviews, surveys and possibly workshops will be organized to collect the requirements of a bigger sample of stakeholders in order to refine and finalize the last version of the tool for all pilot cities. Please note that you are free to choose how many steps you want to participate in. You can for example participate in one step, or all of them.

My participation will involve:

- A Group Interview.
- I am required to participate in the discussion by answering questions.
- The interview will take place online (Microsoft Teams).
- The interview is set to take +/- 1.5 hours.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096406.

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1. Consent form

I have been provided with information about the task and my rights as a participant.

In relation to this task:

- I agree to take part in the group interview as a participant and complete all the exercises that aim to understand the end users' needs and objectives, which will be linked to the development of the mock-ups of the Neutrality Story Maps tool.
- I agree that my personal data which is gathered during and as the result of my participation in this task will be (i) collected and retained for the purpose of this project, and (ii) accessed and analyzed by the imec-SMIT VUB researchers for the purpose of developing the mock-ups of the Neutrality Story Maps tool.

I acknowledge that:

- My participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from participation at any time without explanation.
- My anonymity is guaranteed, and I will not be identified in publications or otherwise without my express written consent.
- I am aware of the legal ground on which the processing of my personal data is based, namely consent as per Art. 6 (1) (a) GDPR.¹
- I am aware that I might withdraw my consent for the processing of my personal data, however without affecting the lawfulness of the processing prior to the withdrawal of consent.
- I am aware that I have the following rights as a data subject, which I can exercise with the controller:
 - ✓ The right to access.
 - ✓ The right to rectification.
 - ✓ The right to erasure.
 - ✓ The right to restriction of processing.
 - ✓ The right to be informed about recipients after a request for rectification, erasure or restriction of processing.
 - ✓ The right to data portability.
 - ✓ The right to object.
 - ✓ The right not to be subjected to automated individual decision-making, including profiling.
 - ✓ To file a complaint to my national Data Protection Authority.
- I am aware that the controller and processor of my personal data provided in the context of this

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UP2030 Consent Form

participation is VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel), Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels, company number 449.012.406. If you have questions or if you wish to exercise your rights, you can contact Milutin Djuraskovic (milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be) or the data protection officer of VUB (dpo@vub.be).

- I am aware that the recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data are VUB.
- I have been informed of the procedure on how to exercise these rights with the controller, namely: sending an e-mail to milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be or the data protection officer of VUB (dpo@vub.be).
- I am aware of the purposes for which my data is gathered and processed in this project, namely: collecting user requirements based on which mock-ups of the Neutrality Story Maps will be developed.
- My data will be protected and kept safe throughout this project and accessed and analysed by imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel researchers for the purpose of implementing this project. My data will be stored for the duration of the project and kept for 5 years after the final payment of Grant Agreement 101096405.

By signing this document, I agree to:

- participate in this group interview under the terms set out above and
- the processing of my personal data

My signature confirms that I accept and understand these conditions without reservation.

Date & Place

Signature

Contact

Milutin Djuraskovic; imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Researcher; Milutin.djuraskovic@vub.be

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 ANNA ΜΑΓΔΑΛΗΝΗ ΒΑΓΓΕΛΑ / ANNA
 MAGDALINI VANGELA
 Father's name: ΔΗΜΗΤΡΙΟΣ / DIMITRIOS
 TIN: 113399924
 Date of signature: 23/04/2024 10:44:50

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